

The Impact of the Digital Markets Act on the Mobile Browser Market: The case of Apple's choice screen*.

Robin Ferreira¹

May 6, 2025

Abstract

In response to the Digital Markets Act (DMA) gatekeepers implement remedies for their services. Whether these remedies have the expected impact on the DMA goals is still a factor of discussion. This paper evaluates the impact of the “Choice Screen” to select the default browser implemented by Apple in all iPhones within the European Union (EU) in order to comply with the DMA. Using information from the App Store, it is observed that browser downloads increased exponentially after the implementation of the choice screen remedy. However, estimates show that there are no statistically significant changes in the mobile market share of Safari and Chrome, which together account for 90% of the mobile browser market usage. For browsers such as Firefox, Opera, and Ecosia the market share increases due to the remedy 0,15%, 0,17%, and 0,05%, respectively. While these changes are small related to the total market share, they represent growth of 24%, 28%, and 102%, relatively to their pre-treatment market share values. An analysis of the compliance reports from Google and Apple reveals that a lack of clear definitions in the architectural elements of the remedy has led to discrepancies in its implementation. It is recommended a revision of alternative remedies accounting for behavioral strategies that could induce learning and / or changes into the remedy specifications regarding the choice screen, thereby improving the effectiveness of the policy.

Keywords: Tying, Digital Markets Act, Choice Screen, Gatekeeper, Browser, Safari

* The views and opinions expressed in this paper are those of the author. I would like to thank Reinhold Kesler, Kai Fischer, and Isabella Bismanns for their comments and support.

¹ Robin.ferreira@dice.hhu.de, +49 163 7715883, Düsseldorf Institute for Competition Economics (DICE), Heinrich-Heine-Universität (HHU), Thesis to obtain the grade of MSc. in Economics. Sup. Dr. Prof. Heidhues Paul, Matrikel-Nr 3212840, SS25

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List of Abbreviations

ACCC – Australian Competition and Consumer Commission	OECD – Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development
CPC – Cost per Click	OEM – Original Equipment Manufacturer
DiD – Difference in Differences	OS – Operating System
DMA – Digital Markets Act	OTA – Online Travel Agencies
EC – European Commission	PPC – Price Parity Clauses
EEA – European Economic Area	SUTVA – Stable Unit Treatment Value Assumption
EU – European Union	UX – User Experience
FTC – Federal Trade Commission	UI – User Interface
IE – Internet Explorer	VPN – Virtual Private Network
IO – Industrial Organization	

1. Introduction

Digital ecosystems are loose networks of interacting organizations that are digitally connected and enabled by modularity, and that affect and are affected by each other's offerings ([Valdez-De-Leon, 2019, pag. 44](#)). These ecosystems play a key role in facilitating interactions between agents and serving as intermediaries within various markets. One example is the browser platforms, which serve as the principal access point to the internet and the starting point for all markets within internet. Over the past decade, browsers have evolved into something more complex, resembling experience-driven products with new tools and functions that offer a range of services to users, driven by the increasing demand and diversity of consumer preferences.

This trend of growth is expected to continue. In 2024, the browser market was estimated to be worth \$236,63 billion, of which \$58,47 billion came from the mobile browser market. Projections for 2033 estimate that the total browser market value will reach \$848 billion and \$111,39 billion for the mobile browser market ([Business Research Insights, 2025](#)). The market value of browsers has continued to grow, while the number of relevant competitors stayed the same. Digital platform markets are characterized by extensive global economies of scale and scope, powerful networks and ecosystem effects and significant data feedback loops. All of these characteristics tend to drive concentration within markets and facilitate the extension of favorable markets position across markets ([Fletcher et al., 2024, p. 2](#)).

Since 2009, the market share of the top 10 browsers has accounted for an average of 98%, with the two principal competitors, Chrome and Safari, holding an average share of 92% ([StatCounter, 2024](#)). Consequently, accusations of anticompetitive practices have emerged, since 2017, Google has been fined for diverse anticompetitive reasons like favoring its own shopping service, restricting competition, abuse their dominance in the online advertising market, violations of data protection and breaching intellectual property ([Horne, 2024](#)).

In July 2018, the European Commission (EC) fined Google €4,34 billion for illegal practices, specifically tying, related to Android mobile with Google's search engine. One accusation specifically related to their browser platform, state “...*the tying of Google Chrome with the Play Store and the Google Search App since 1 August 2012. In particular, Google has*

mandated manufacturers to pre-install the Google Search app and browser app (Chrome) as a condition for licensing Google's app store -Play Store”² § Art.1(3).

Similar accusations of anticompetitive practices continue to follow Google and later also Apple, particularly in markets like the US³, UK⁴ and Australia where the Australian Competition & Consumer Commission (ACCC) was one of the first organizations to raise the need for new regulation in digital platforms. In a recent response to the ACCC, Apple highlighted the potential consequences of over-regulation using the DMA as an example: “...that regulation can degrade consumer experiences, including by introducing safety, security and privacy risks, by having a chilling effect on innovation, as well as potentially curtailing the suite of services available to Australian businesses and consumers due to regulatory aversion or uncertainty -as has already been observed in Europe... ([Apple Aus, 2024, p.2](#))”. The necessity for innovative regulations that ensure effectiveness, fairness, and user protection in digital markets, without limiting innovation has led authorities to shift their focus toward new competition policies, driven by a shared concern about the intrinsic tendency of these ecosystems to become concentrated. ([Calvano & Polo, 2021](#)).

The EC launched a proposal named the Digital Markets Act (DMA) at the end of 2020 as the EU’s law to make the digital market fairer and more contestable. To do so, the DMA establishes a set of clearly defined objective criteria to identify gatekeepers (companies that meet specific criteria). The DMA came into force in November 2022 and the further designation of six gatekeepers: Alphabet, Amazon, Apple, ByteDance, Meta and Microsoft, mandates them to ensure compliance with the obligations and prohibitions in the different core platform services. In Apple’s case the gatekeeper designation was for their core platforms “App store”, operation system “iOS” and their web browser “Safari” having until

² European Commission, Antitrust Procedure decision of 18.07.2018, Case AT.40099, p. 325

³ U.S. and Plaintiff States v. Google LLC [2020]. Verdict ruled against Google who acted illegally to maintain a monopoly in online search. Last update: A trial will be held in April 2025 with potential remedies, a ruling is expected by August 2025 <https://www.justice.gov/atr/case/us-and-plaintiff-states-v-google-llc>.

U.S and Plaintiff States v. Apple Inc. [2024] Case ongoing. Apple accused of maintaining competitive threats in order to protect their smartphone monopolies. Last update: Waiting Court decision to Apple motion to dismiss the case. <https://www.justice.gov/atr/case/us-and-plaintiff-states-v-apple-inc>

⁴ CMA Accusation “Mobile browser and cloud gaming”. (2002) Last update: Provisional decision in favor to the CMA, and waiting for the final report publication in February-March 2025 <https://www.gov.uk/cma-cases/mobile-browsers-and-cloud-gaming#primary-research>.

August 2024 to comply. As result, Apple published their compliance report, a series of remedies in order to comply with the DMA articles.

This paper analyzes one of these remedies implemented related to the browser core platform designation, specifically the one stated in Article 6(3) of the DMA, the implementation of the choice screen to select the default browser. The investigation is based on the following two research questions:

- (1) What is the effect of Apple's implementation of the 'About Your Default Browser' choice screen on downloads and market share of iOS mobile browsers?*
- (2) What evidence-based modifications could be implemented to achieve a fairer and more contestable remedy in the browser market?*

In order to answer these questions, empirical methodology and literature review in behavioral economics about the effectiveness of screen interventions and policy interventions will be discussed. As [Cabral et al. \(2021, p.7\)](#) considered, one of the main challenges in the implementation of the DMA is how to separate the positive efficiency and welfare gains that platforms generate through network effects from negative anti-competitive and welfare-reducing platform behaviour. Therefore, the main limitation of this paper, and the opportunity for further research, is the general welfare analysis of the remedy.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: [Section 2](#) presents a literature review on the role of defaults in digital markets, the consequences of DMA restrictions, and recommendations for an effective DMA implementation. [Section 3](#) introduces the institutional background, providing context on the browser market, its relationship with the DMA, the designation of gatekeepers in the browser core platform, and the corresponding remedies. [Section 4](#) presents a descriptive analysis and outlines the empirical model used to evaluate the effects of Apple's remedy. [Section 5](#) details the results of the analysis, followed by [Section 6](#), which discusses the findings in greater depth, recalling the research questions and the article limitations. Finally, [Section 7](#) concludes the paper.

2. Related Literature

This paper is relevant to three levels of literature (i) into the consequences of defaults through behavioral techniques, (ii) into the consequences of DMA restrictions and (iii) into recommendations of an effective DMA implementation.

Regarding (i), to the behavioral Industrial Organization (IO) literature on the evidence of the consequences of defaults in digital markets. [Heidhues et al. \(2024\)](#) study steering strategy through defaults and give an explanation to the creation of digital ecosystems, where an incentive to cross-market steering exists. The market leaders that control the “access point” markets will end growing into ecosystems taking over market leaders (understood as best products) in adjacent markets, with a winner(s) take all result.

Evidence of this is the Google's agreements with distributors (i.e. device manufacturers, major wireless carriers and browser developers) and anticompetitive conducts to lock up distribution channels blocking rivals. For the browser platforms exists an incentive to set as default their own products (or being paid otherwise) and steer consumers into their ecosystems by pre-selecting services like the search engine, using data to manipulate consumer attention or setting products as consumer reference points, e.g. Apple tying Safari or Google tying Chrome.

The market dominance of players like Google is partly a consequence of controlling the entry points to the browser market. As an example, [Hovenkamp \(2024\)](#) demonstrates the market effects and dynamics of default using the search engine market. In his model, search platforms are horizontally differentiated by the quality advantage that network effects give to their algorithms; more users = higher quality advantage. And vertically differentiated by the “ad intensity”. Showing that if the algorithm learning effects were extremely strong with increasing returns, then consumers could be better off under monopoly than competition. However, algorithmic learning effects have diminishing marginal returns, which means that after a certain point the marginal effect of increasing product quality and hence consumer welfare will become too costly (in terms of browser user base vs other browsers). What defaults cause then for the dominant platform is a marginal positive impact in product quality but higher market power, reflected in the increase of the “ad intensity” variable, reducing consumer welfare. Moreover, they show that in this case defaults suppress entry and

investment competition. However, defaults can stimulate competition and increase consumer welfare when they are applied to laggards.

Analyzing the dynamics of default at firm and market level is relevant for the general equilibrium, but equally important is understanding why defaults are sticky. Using an experimental design, [Allcott et al. \(2025\)](#) observed the impact of default at an individual level and provide an explanation using behavioral factors such as inattention and naivety in quality beliefs.

They develop a model of demand for search engines using US desktop internet users, showing that using an active screen to select their default search engine (similar to the remedy studied in this paper) increases Chrome rivalry option, Bing, only by 1,1% and imply that switching costs play a limited role. Moreover, they create different treatment groups with payment incentives to try Bing for two weeks. The participants who accepted updated their quality beliefs positively related to Bing, and 33% continued to use it after the experiment indicating that defaults create a lasting mismatch between preferences and choices. In their model, correcting beliefs and removing choice frictions would increase Bing's market share by 15% and increase consumer surplus by \$6 per consumer per year.

Lastly, they show that sharing Google's click and query data with Microsoft (Bing) may have a limited effect on market shares, implying that algorithmic learning in a quality product differentiation is less relevant to consumer demand, at least for the search engine market with products of a certain quality threshold. The results of this paper go in line with their findings, even when switching costs and inattention are reduced to the minimum, defaults matter by preventing consumers from gaining experience with alternative browsers whose quality they initially underestimate.

Another paper that gives behavioral insights and shows the potential causes of default effects, their consequences and intervention recommendations is [Duque \(2024\)](#). He conducted an experiment in which participants could answer some technical questions by searching the internet using different default search engines (Google, Bing and Yahoo). After the exposure to either Bing or Yahoo, participants increased their perceived quality of the default and decreased their perceived quality of Google. The effect is clear and statistically significant for Bing but subtle and not statistically significant for Yahoo. Interestingly, both Yahoo and

Bing use the same search algorithm, giving the same answers to participants. However, their user interface (UI) is very different, meaning that UI is an essential product attribute together with the perceived quality of the rivals and the user experience on digital product election.

There is a growing branch of literature on the consequences of steering and self-preferencing through other behavioral strategies, similarly to defaults, used to influence user behavior and maintain market power. [Li \(2024\)](#) studied ancillary products, complements of the core services offered in the primary market, showing that self-preferencing can generate severe negative effects on both buyers and sellers in the long run. For example, the self-preferencing strategies used by Amazon in their different markets and algorithms.

In the Amazon eBook market [Reimers and Waldfogel \(2023\)](#) found evidence of ranking bias, with Amazon books ranked 23,6% higher than non-Amazon books. In the “Frequently Bought Together” product recommendation feature, [Chen and Tsai \(2024\)](#) found that Amazon Products sold by Amazon receive on average 1.55 more recommendations than third-party products. In Amazon’s search result algorithm, [Farronato et al. \(2023\)](#) found that average Amazon products are given three positions greater prominence appearing closer to the top compared to non-amazon products. More recently, [Etro \(2024\)](#) analyzes the welfare impact of Amazon’s dual role, sharing a more conservative view that the trade-offs of the dual role are complex and that it is not yet possible to conclude that banning Amazon's dual model would benefit consumers. For this analysis, it is believed that banning steering and self-preference for gatekeepers are equally important as the tying strategies (by defaults) in the goal of achieving a more competitive market.

Regarding (ii) the consequences of the DMA restrictions. Since the publication of the DMA there is no empirical report that analyzes the impact regarding gatekeeper compliance strategies with Article 6(3) and Article 6(4) in relation to tying and steering through defaults in the browser market.

The empirical methodology of this paper is based on [Decarolis et al. \(2024\)](#) where they studied the search engine market of different but connected policies in the banning of steering through defaults. Based in a causal Difference in Differences (DiD) model, the paper concludes that interventions involving consumer choices via a choice screen can have a small impact on online search market competition, unless there is a qualified challenger who can

compete with Google on quality or a rival who has the means and motivation to replace Google by investing in the local market. In an extension of their research, they found that almost two years after the introduction of the choice screen, Google's mobile market share was still 97,66%, a change of less than 1% since the introduction of the Android choice screen.

Recent literature has been published regarding DMA consequences and the ban of other anticompetitive strategies. For example, Regarding self-preference stated in Article 6(5) of the DMA, [Waldfoegel \(2024\)](#) found that shortly after the designation of Amazon as a gatekeeper, the Amazon rank differential in their search results fell from a 30-position advantage to a 20-position advantage, while other major brands' positions in the ranking were unaffected. Interestingly this change was also observed in non-EU countries. In general, Amazon substantially lowered their search ranks for its own products, not surprising considering the lawsuits in other countries like the one in the Federal Trade Commission (FTC) in the USA at that time.

Regarding Article 6(3) related to steering strategy. In [Pape and Rossi \(2024\)](#) studied the effects of the "Google Maps" removal within their search engine results, for example when looking for a restaurant, hotel, etc. Consequently, more queries related to "maps" were made, but the decrease in Google Maps visits was not significant, meaning that this extra step resulted in a loss of consumer welfare calculated in approximately 3,3 million euros per year.

Related to Article 5(3) of the DMA which includes the prohibition of all types of price parity clauses (PPC) whenever gatekeeper platforms are involved, and which booking.com was the first designated gatekeeper. [Ma et al. \(2024\)](#) studied PPC in the case of online bookings and found that after the ban, bookings through Online Travel Agencies (OTA) were reduced by 2,1% and the prices on hotels primary offline channel (e-mails, calls, walks-in) were on average 5,7% lower than the prices displayed in OTAs.

In relation to (iii) the literature recommendations for an effective implementation of the DMA. The most similar paper to this one regarding effectiveness is from [Åkesson et al. \(2023\)](#). They run an experimental study simulating the choice screen required by the EU for the browser market under diverse treatments in the choice architecture of the screen to select the users default browser. The takeaways are in favor of the screen implementation vs not,

better results when the choice screen shows more browsers and more information than when it shows fewer browsers and less information and shows that the best time to prompt the choice screen is during phone set-up rather than after the first click in the pre-selected browser. However, they conclude that choice screens alone will not necessarily be sufficient to address competition concerns. Given the maturity of the browser market, with a long-held pattern of behaviour built up over time, a more active intervention will be required.

[Decarolis and Li \(2023\)](#) use a theoretical model for the mobile search engine market and they recommend that quality enhancement, data portability and consumer awareness of how data is collected and monetized should play a key role in the remedies implemented by the gatekeepers. Consequently, the remedies should have a more significant impact than the results of the Android search engine choice screen implemented in March 2020. The majority of research recommendations are primarily designed around the search engine market, where the quality of the product is affected by network effect and algorithm learning. However, awareness and quality enhancement can be equally applied in the browser market.

[Duque \(2024\)](#) demonstrates, using the recent cases of the active choice screen in the EU that an incomplete analysis of the contingency of people's behaviour had misguided enforcement efforts and led policymakers to adopt counterproductive remedies. Concepts like regret aversion, implicit recommendation, endowment effect, procrastination and principally misperception about quality of competitors made defaults sticky. Then, he recommends understanding the default types: (i) users are relatively satisfied with the default option (good defaults), (ii) users are not aware of competing alternatives to defaults, and/or (iii) users misperceive their quality (bad defaults) and act accordingly on the design for an efficient policy implementation.

[Heidhues et al. \(2023\)](#) provide a concise overview of the possible actions that could make the search engine market more competitive. A generalization of the search engine recommendations to the browser market can be applied. For example, prohibiting dominant platforms from purchasing exclusive default positions or deploying contractual restrictions through prominence or default status. Another option is to prohibit dominant platforms from enforcing contracts that require pre-installation of specific browsers or give control over the designs of the home screen. For other recommendations, the browser can act as an active

agent for a fairer search market for example by prohibiting search engines to self-prefer their products while using their browser, or by setting search engine randomization as default.

Overall, policymakers need to take behavioral theories into account when creating remedies. Moreover, to target trade restraints that block disruptive innovation (e.g. search engine-browser contracts) and to implement a dedicated application to manage defaults, e.g. using the choice screen as a complement to default assignation strategy, a reiterate strategy in recent literature.

An important number of papers analyze the DMA from a structural point of view and regarding possible improvements of the state remedies. [Cabral et al. \(2021\)](#) from the Joint Research Centre propose a series of actions to be added or better defined in the articles of the DMA, e.g. the specification of behavioral actions of gatekeepers such as tying, bundling and self-preference, the use and definition of price thresholds within app- stores, the necessity of a deeper analysis on the topic of mergers and acquisitions and the lack of definition of fairness and means of measurement.

Other frequently cited work in this area is [De Streel et al. \(2023\)](#), a paper recompilation divided into three sections: gatekeeper designation, obligations and process and institutional design. It is part of a larger project entitled “Effective and Proportionate implementation of the DMA”, a collection of nine papers focusing on the trade-offs around the different possible interpretation of the regulation. The compilation is similar to a guide of DMA recommendations with an emphasis on the gatekeeper’s obligations.

[Fletcher et al. \(2024\)](#) flagged issues in the definitions and interpretations within articles and the lack of procedures for the evaluation of the DMA. Therefore, they highlight the use of economic analysis for the evaluation of the DMA, such as using behavioral economic vision for compliance evidence. Lastly [Peitz \(2023\)](#) highlighted the interpretation issues on the prohibition of self-preferencing in Article 6(5) of the DMA.

3. Institutional Background

Chapter 3 is presented using a deductive approach. [Subchapter 3.1](#) begins by providing context on how the mobile browser market evolved into its current state. [Subchapter 3.2](#) describes the context and composition of how the DMA was constituted. From this point onward, the institutional background will focus on the browser core platform service. [Subchapter 3.3](#) presents a summary of the initial gatekeeper designations under the DMA and outlines their obligations. [Subchapter 3.4](#) delves into the gatekeepers' compliance remedies and explores literature recommendations for effective remedy implementation. [Subchapter 3.5](#) presents and describes Apple's choice screen remedy, while [Subchapter 3.6](#) outlines its implementation characteristics and initial outcomes.

3.1 Mobile Browser Market

The mobile browser market began to rise in the 2000s with the introduction of smartphones capable of connecting to the internet. At that time, Internet Explorer (IE), Microsoft's browser for PCs, was available on 90% of the world's computers, reaching a peak market share of 95% in 2005⁵. This dominance resulted from Microsoft's strategy of tying IE to Windows Operating System (OS) as the default (and only) preinstalled browser. Reason for which, in 2009, the EC accused Microsoft of harming competition, undermining product innovation, and ultimately reducing consumer welfare⁶.

In response, Microsoft committed to the EU that it would display a choice screen, allowing Windows users to select which web browsers they wanted to install in addition to - or instead of—Microsoft's IE browser. However, a series of technical errors and omissions led to Microsoft's failure to provide the choice screen. As a result, in 2013, the EC fined Microsoft €561 million for failing to comply with its commitment⁷.

⁵ Web browser market is understood as users of PCs that access and interact with web content hosted on servers that are connected to networks such as the internet, meanwhile mobile browser market refers to the same access users but that access and interact through the use of smartphones

⁶ European Commission, MEMO 09/15 of 17.01.2009 - Ref. case T-201/04.

⁷ European Commission, Decision of 16.12.2009 – Ref. case AT.39530.3, Microsoft (tying), §Section 5.6 (79)

Despite this omission, IE was decreasing since 2005, caused by the entry of new competitors like Firefox (2004), offering a better interface, greater speed and, above all, compatibility with mobile OS for which IE is not supported⁸. As a Google executive stated, *"It's hard to believe, but we are on the verge of a tipping point. It is possible that in 2009, more internet capable smartphones will ship than desktop PCs. [...] These changes are opening up opportunities for Google. Today, almost a third of all Google searches in Japan are coming from mobile devices. This is leading indicator of where the rest of the world will be soon"*⁹.

This shift was primarily caused by Apple's mobile release: the iPhone, launched in early 2008, becoming one of the most successful technological product releases, with over 11 million units sold in 2008 and 21 million sold in 2009¹⁰ ([Statista, 2024](#)). Through its browser Safari, Apple held a 65% share of total HTML mobile pages views and 65% of global mobile internet and app usage in 2009. That same year, Safari became the most-used mobile browser, capturing 33% of the mobile browser market ([Morgan Stanley, 2009](#)).

Unlike the web browser market, the mobile browser market was relatively new, with Safari leading the way. However, new mobile manufacturers were developing their own OS, including browsers, offering a more diverse range of options and contributing to a more distributed market.

In 2009, Safari accounted for 33% of the mobile browser market, followed by Opera with 25,33%, Nokia with 18,96%, and BlackBerry with 9%. While iPhone sales continued to grow in the following years, Safari's market share did not increase proportionally. This was partly due to the overall expansion of the market and the proportional growth of competitors. But more significantly, it was influenced by the rise of what would become the most widely used mobile OS: Android.

⁸ Microsoft IE browser never accounted for more than 2% in the mobile market share

⁹ e-mail of 26.05.2009. from [Google Executive] to Sergey Brin and other Google executives in relation to the 2008 Founders' Letter (Doc ID 1305-39872). Citation taken from European Commission, Decision of 18.07.2018 – Ref. Case AT.40099, Google Android, p.30

¹⁰ iPhone sales continue to growth exponentially until 2015 reaching 231 million that year record that was hold until 2021 were a total of 242 million of iPhone were ship

Led by Google, Android was released in 2008 and described by its creators, the Open Handset Alliance¹¹, as follows: *“The Android platform will be made available under one of the most progressive, developer-friendly open-source licenses, which gives mobile operators and device manufacturers significant freedom and flexibility to design product ... Open handset alliance aims to develop technologies that will significantly lower the cost of developing and distributing mobile devices and services (Open handset Alliance, 2007).*

The alliance’s strategy to position Android was to distribute it as widely as possible by making the OS open source and pre-installing it on every mobile device requested by Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs). For OEMs, the software was offered free of charge. Mobile network operators were allowed to integrate their own apps into Android devices, generating additional revenue streams. Meanwhile, app developers were incentivized to create applications for Android, as its open-source nature fostered a self-reinforcing cycle: more consumers led to more developers, and more developers led to a richer app ecosystem. Through network effects, this approach facilitated the rapid adoption of Android as the default OS for most mobile manufacturers.

Android was successfully adopted and with it all the pre-installed apps. In 2009, the Android browser held a market share of 2,46%. However, within just three years, by 2012, it had grown to match Safari’s market share at approximately 24%. The following year, in 2013 - the only year this occurred – the Android browser surpassed Safari as the most-used mobile browser, reaching a market share of 28,68%.

This trend shifted when Google Chrome, released in 2008, was designated as the default browser for mobile devices running Android 4.0 and later versions. From 2012 onward, Chrome replaced the Android browser on nearly all new Android devices ([Protalinski, 2013](#)). This marked the beginning of Chrome’s exponential growth, in just three years Chrome’s market share went from 0,35% in 2012 to 33,35% in 2015, making it the most widely used mobile browser. Meanwhile, Apple’s Safari saw its market share decline to 18,84%. This highlights the relevance of tying strategies and default position in determining market

¹¹ A total of 34 companies were part of Open handset alliance some of which includes Google, T-Mobile, HTC, Qualcomm, Motorola, China Mobile, eBay, Intel, Nvidia, Samsung, Sprint Nextel etc.

dominance. These rankings in the browser market have persisted to the present day, with Chrome maintaining an average market share of 68% and Safari holding around 23%.

Not only has the browser industry evolved over time in terms of market share, but its value and revenue models have also become much more complex. What initially started as a simple application for processing web content quickly transformed into an ecosystem of products and services.

In 1994, Netscape, one of the first web browsers, and Microsoft developed a solution that allowed websites to track user information across pages, enabling functionalities such as online shopping. This innovation, known as "cookies," are small text files containing data that can be used to identify users or store information, such as a shopping cart ID. Initially, cookies were automatically saved, and browsers exploited them to compile long-term records of users' browsing history, creating extensive marketing profiles that could be sold for significant financial gain. However, it was not until 1996 that privacy concerns surrounding cookies began to emerge ([Jackson, 1996](#)).

Today, browsers generate revenue not only by leveraging consumer data (such as cookies) but also through industry agreements and additional services offered directly to users. One of the most well-known examples is the agreement between web browsers and Google's search engine, in which Google pays to be set as the default search engine across various browsers. In 2021, Google paid \$510 million to be the default search engine on Mozilla's Firefox browser.¹² Meanwhile in 2022, it was estimated that Google paid Apple approximately \$20 billion to secure its position as the default search engine on Safari—accounting for around 15% of Apple's operating profit that year.

At the consumer level, browsers offer various subscription-based services with advanced security features, Virtual Private Networks (VPN), and cloud storage solutions, such as *Brave Premium*, *Mozilla Monitor Plus*, and *Opera VPN Pro*. Prices and services vary depending on the provider. For example, *Brave Premium* offers different extensions and packages ranging from \$3 to \$14,99 per month. Mozilla provides *Mozilla VPN* and *Mozilla Monitor*, priced at

¹² Google's payment accounted for 86% of Mozilla's revenue in 2021-2022
<https://www.newsbytesapp.com/news/science/google-s-antitrust-ruling-poses-threat-to-mozilla-s-firefox/story>

\$8,99 and \$13,99 per month, respectively. Meanwhile, *Opera VPN Pro* offers different payment options, costing between €4 and €8 per month.

Additionally, browsers generate revenue through data usage, such as selling anonymized user information for targeted advertising—examples include *Google Ads* and *Brave Ads*. *Google Ads* operates on a cost-per-click (CPC) model, where advertisers pay for each click a user makes on ads displayed through Google’s browser. Various options allow advertisers to set an average daily or monthly budget for their ad campaigns. In comparison, *Brave Ads* offers multiple pricing models, including flat rates for "new tab" takeovers, cost-per-impression and CPC (similar to Google Ads). Furthermore, browsers can monetize their homepage or "new tab" page by segmenting ads based on user characteristics or geographic location. For example, Firefox’s *Pocket Recommendations* feature promoted articles or content, earning referral fees.

More recently, some browsers have also begun selling data for AI training. *Brave Search API*, for instance, is used to train search engines, with different pricing plans available. The free version allows one query per second, while the *Pro* package costs \$9 per month and provides up to 50 queries per second as training data. While browser services have evolved into a diverse range of products, they all rely on the same network effect principle in the development of their services: benefiting from a larger user base and increased browser usage to enhance their offerings.

3.2 Digital Markets Act

On December 15, 2020, the EC published a proposal for the DMA¹³ with the objective of ensuring more “contestable” and “fair” markets in the digital sector—particularly for business users and end users of core platform services provided by gatekeepers. Weak contestability and unfair practices in the digital sector are more prevalent and pronounced in certain digital services than in others. Therefore, the scope of the DMA is limited to a number of *core platform services* that exhibit the following characteristics: (i) highly concentrated

¹³ European Commission, Proposal of 15.12.2020 (2020) – Ref. COM(2020) 842, Proposal for a regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on contestable and fair markets in the digital sector (Digital Markets Act)

multi-sided platform services, where usually one or very few large digital platforms set the commercial conditions (ii) and act as gateways for business users to reach their customers and vice-versa.

The core platform services were defined as (i) online intermediation services (incl. e.g. marketplaces, app stores and online intermediation services in other sectors like mobility, transport or energy), (ii) online search engines, (iii) social networks (iv) video sharing platform services, (v) number independent interpersonal electronic communication services, (vi) operating systems, (vii) cloud services and (viii) advertising services (incl. advertising networks, advertising exchanges and other advertising intermediation services, where these advertising services are being related to one or more of the other core platform services mentioned above). However, the classification of a digital service as core platform service does not automatically subject its providers to the obligations of the DMA. Only gatekeepers must comply with the articles.

A provider of core platform services is designated as a gatekeeper if it meets the following conditions: (a) significant impact on the internal digital market, (b) it provides a core platform service which is an important gateway for business users to reach end users; and (c) it enjoys an entrenched and durable position, in its operations, or it is foreseeable that it will enjoy such a position in the near future § Art.3(1).

In general, the DMA consists of five chapters and 39 articles, outlining its scope definitions, obligations, enforcements and penalties. The structure of the DMA can be divided as follows:

Chapter 1: General provisions (Articles 1-3)

- Article 1 – Subject Matter & Scope: Defines the purpose of the DMA
- Article 2 – Provide definitions, Gatekeeper, core platform, interoperability, etc.
- Article 3 – Specification and designation of Gatekeeper: Lists criteria for companies to be classified as Gatekeeper.

Chapter 2: Obligations for gatekeepers (Articles 2-15). “dos” and “don’ts” that gatekeepers must comply with in their daily operations.

- Article 5 – Obligations without need for further specification (strict rules for gatekeepers)
- Article 6 – Obligations subject to further specification (More technical compliance)
- Article 7 – Ensuring interoperability for messaging services.

- Article 8;13 – Procedural aspects of compliance, exemptions, and implementation timelines.
- Article 14 – Merger reporting
- Article 15 – Auditing of profiling techniques

Chapter 3: Market investigations.

- Article 16 – Market investigations to designate Gatekeepers
- Article 17 – Investigations into Systemic Non-Compliance
- Article 18 – Investigations into new services & practices

Chapter 4: Enforcement and penalties (Articles 20-31)

- Article 29 – Fines and penalties (10% of global turnover for non-compliance and up to 20% for repeated violations)

Chapter 5: Final provisions (Articles 32 – 39) Covers legal aspects, regulatory review and transitional measures.

The DMA includes a list of 22 prohibitions and obligations, a summary table can be found in [Appendix Table A.1](#), that can be divided into three distinct provisions. Article 5 enumerates nine items, primarily prohibitions, which are intended to be self-explanatory. Article 6 lists twelve items, mostly obligations, which may require further clarification or specification by the EC; and finally, Article 7 introduces a horizontal interoperability obligation for communication applications, requiring phased implementation due to its complexity.

The DMA regulation was adopted on September 14, 2022¹⁴. published in the Official Journal on October 12¹⁵ and came into force on May 2, 2023. Within two months of that date, companies providing core platform services had to notify the EC about whether they met the quantitative thresholds for the designation as gatekeepers §Art. 3(3) and provide all relevant information. These thresholds are specified in §Art. 3(2) and can be divided into (a) size and impact in the EU market; annual turnover of at least €7.5 billion in the EU in the last three financial years or with a market capitalization of at least €75 billion in the last financial year and provide the core platform services in at least three EU member states. (b) Large user base, with at least 45 million monthly active end users in the EU and more than 10.000 yearly

¹⁴ European Parliament & Council of the European Union, Decision of 14.09.2022 – Ref. L265/1, Regulation (EU) 2022/1925 on contestable and fair markets in the digital sector (Digital Markets Act).

¹⁵ European Union, Official Journal Vol.65, Legislation of 12.10.2022 – Ref. L265(65), p.1-67.

active business users established in the EU. (c) Entrenchment and sustainability. The user thresholds described in point (b) Large use base should be met in each of the last three financial years.

Once notified by the gatekeeper, the commission has 45 working days to adopt a decision designating a specific gatekeeper §Art. 3(4). After the designation, gatekeepers have a maximum of six months after the EC’s decision to ensure compliance with the obligations and prohibitions laid down in the DMA §Art. 3(10), ([EC Press release, 2022](#)).

3.3 Designation of Browser Gatekeepers

On 6 September 2024, Alphabet, Amazon, Apple, ByteDance, Meta and Microsoft were the first companies to be designated as gatekeepers in various core platform services. On April 29, 2024, Apple's OS for tablets, and on May 13, 2024, the intermediation service Booking.com were added to the list. In total, 24 core platform services provided by these gatekeepers have been designated¹⁶ as summarized in table 1.

Tab. 1: Gatekeepers’ designation by Core Platform Service.

Alphabet		Amazon		Apple		Booking		Byte		Meta		Microsoft	
Ads	Browser	Intermediation		N-IICS		Operating System		Search		Social Network		Video Sharing	
Google	Chrome	Google Maps		WhatsApp		Google Android		Google Search		TikTok		YouTube	
Amazon	Safari	Google Play		Messenger		iOS				Facebook			
Meta		Google Shopping				iPadOS				Instagram			
		Amazon Marketplace				Windows PC OS				LinkedIn			
		App Store											
		Booking.com											
		Meta Marketplace											

Source of data: European Commission (2024), Gatekeepers designation.

Due to the objective of this analysis, the focus will be on the browser core platform service. A browser, following the definition in the DMA is "a software application that enables end users to access and interact with web content hosted on servers that are connected to networks such as the Internet, including standalone web browsers as well as web browsers integrated or embedded in software or similar §Art. 2(11) ".

¹⁶ All 24-gatekeeper core platform service designation cases can be found in https://digital-markets-act.ec.europa.eu/gatekeepers_en

Apple, Google, Microsoft and Samsung were candidates to be designated as gatekeepers due to their respective browser platforms. Samsung with their browser "Samsung Internet browser" met the requirements to be designated as a gatekeeper platform. However, Samsung was able to prove that it did not meet the relevant criteria for designation, arguing that its scale and importance was significantly lower compared to Chrome and Safari. Additionally, the declining trend in the browser's usage since 2016, along with other factors, led to a modification of its designation¹⁷. A similar situation occurred with Microsoft, whose web browser "Bing" was initially designated as a gatekeeper, being part of the Microsoft platform ecosystem. However, Microsoft presented arguments based on the number of search queries and clicks, claiming that the scale of its activities was limited. The EC assessed these and other arguments and ultimately decided to modify Bing's designation¹⁸. As a result, the final resolution designated Google Chrome, part of Alphabet, and Safari, part of Apple, as the only gatekeepers in the browser platform.

Each gatekeeper must adhere to and provide evidence of their compliance with the obligations laid down principally in §/Art 5, 6, and 7. [De Streel et al. \(2023,p.39\)](#), summarizes the obligations and prohibitions of these articles which can be found in [Appendix Table 1](#). This paper evaluates specifically §Art. 6(3) in the browser market.

§ Art. 6(3)

*(a) Allow and technically enable end users to **easily un-install any software applications on the operating system of the gatekeeper**, without prejudice to the possibility for that gatekeeper to restrict such uninstallation in relation to software applications that are essential for the functioning of the operating system or of the device and which cannot technically be offered on a standalone basis by third parties.*

*(b) allow and technically enable end users to easily change default settings on the operating system and web browser of the gatekeeper that direct or steer end users to products or services provided by the gatekeeper; **this includes prompting end users, at the moment of the end users' first use of a web browser of the gatekeeper listed in the designation decision pursuant to Article 3(9) of Regulation (EU) 2022/1925, to choose, from a list of the main available service providers, the web browser to which the operating system of the gatekeeper directs or steers users by default, and the***

¹⁷ European Commission, decision of 05.09.2023 – Ref. Case DMA.100038, Samsung – Web browsers.

¹⁸ European Commission, decision of 12.02.2024 – Ref. Case DMA. 100028, Microsoft Web browsers.

online search engine to which the web browser of the gatekeeper directs or steers users by default.

In summary (a) Apple should allow users to uninstall Safari in iPhones, meanwhile Google should allow users to uninstall Chrome in Androids (b) Apple and Google should display an active choice screen to select the default browser.

In response Apple submitted its compliance report to the EC ([Apple, 2024](#)) pursuant to §/Art 11. According to the report, Apple announced plans to take the following measures with respect to § Art. 6(3):

*(a) Apple has enabled end users to un-install every app on iOS except for Safari, Settings, App Store, Phone, Messages, Camera and Photos, which can be removed from the Home Screen but not un-installed entirely. As concerns **Safari**, Apple has announced that it **will make it fully un-installable by the end of 2024.***

*(b) Apple has enabled end users to **switch default settings** on iOS in relation to **web browsers**, mail applications, app marketplace applications and contactless payments applications. In addition, Apple has announced that it will also introduce a new default control for users for navigation applications by March 2025.*

*(c) Apple has prompted end users with a **choice screen to select their default web browser** on iOS once they install the iOS 17.4 update and open Safari for the first time. For each Member State, the choice screen includes Safari alongside 11 third-party web browsers which are the most downloaded browsers on iOS in these countries in the prior year and shows them in a randomized order per user.*

The EC opened a proceeding to examine whether the measures taken by Apple comply with the DMA obligations¹⁹. Since Apple's compliance report submission on March 7, 2024, up to today: (a) Safari cannot be un-installable from iPhones²⁰ (b) It is possible to change the

¹⁹ European Commission. Decision of 25.03.2024(2024) – Ref. Case DMA. 1000185 – Apple – Operating systems – iOS – Article 6(3)

²⁰ 22 November 2024. iPhone using the latest system available iOS18.1.1. Evidence of DICE Research, HHU.

default browser and mail but not the Marketplace App and Contactless Payments. (c) After the update, the browser choice screen is displayed as described.

In the compliance report submitted by Google and published on March 6, 2024 ([Google 2024, p.126](#)), stated that (a) the uninstallation obligation of Art. 6(3) does not apply to Google Chrome because it applies to designated operating system CPSs; and (b) it will implement the browser choice screen on all Android OS devices that have Google Chrome as the default, with the exception of OEM Samsung which default browser is Samsung Internet browser.

Google's choice screen applies to both new and existing Android devices in the following manner: Since March 6, 2024, Google Pixel users see the choice screen after OS update. For new Google-approved mobile devices from OEMs, choice screens are mandated to be included during the setup wizard. For already-approved third-party mobile devices, Google does not control third-party devices. However, Google has made an update available that includes the choice screen and has encouraged OEMs to load this update into their devices.

As part of HHU DICE's research program, the process of changing default settings on five occasions over a one-year period on mobile devices Google Pixel A03 and iPhone SE was recorded²¹. These processes were conducted after a factory reset, using devices and chips purchased within the EU.

For the Google Pixel A03 no choice screen for search engines or browsers could be observed, despite the statement in Google's compliance report regarding the update on March 6, 2024. According to the official Android page "[Browser choice screen](#)" cited in Google's compliance report ([Google, 2024, p.129](#)) the browser choice screen was expected to start appearing on new devices distributed in the European Economic Area (EEA) on or after August 7, 2024. An analysis of Google's progress in implementing this feature would help understand the degree of compliance.

In comparison, Apple released iOS 17.4 on March 6, 2024, which included the "About your default browser" screen, prompt to old and new devices that have set the Safari browser as

²¹ Updates in Oct 2023, Jan 2024, April 2024, May 2024, Sep 2024. Ppt can be found in: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14790405>

default and transitioned to iOS 17.4. This could be corroborated by the DICE institute in both set-up processes made after the update release date

3.4 Compliance remedy

Implementing the choice screen was only one step towards the DMA objectives, providers have an incentive to modify the “choice architecture” elements presented in the choice screens to steer the user’s decision in order to strengthen, consolidate, and /or extend their market positions, in the market itself or across markets ([Fletcher et al. 2024, p.2](#)). Therefore, the EC should assess the choice screen acknowledging the existence of behavioral elements or “dark patterns” that could diminish the intended effect. For example, the “default effect”, which is the tendency to accept the default option ([Jachimowicz et al. 2019](#)); the “ranking effect”, the tendency to choose a higher ranked option; ([Ursu, 2018](#)); the “salient effect”, the tendency to choose more salient or prominent options; and the “recommendation effect” where users perceive the default option as a recommendation from the gatekeeper. Additionally it should consider, “choice overload”, when people become overwhelmed by too many options ([Chernev, 2015](#)) and “choice fatigue” when people disengaged if they are asked to make too many decisions ([Pignatiello et al., 2020](#)).

[De Streel et al. \(2023, p.77-88\)](#), raise questions regarding interpretation and challenges for implementation of the DMA Articles 6(3) and Article 6(4), which can serve as a starting point to avoid the dark patterns. The questions are divided into scope issues, effectiveness issues and mitigating unintended consequences. Some of these questions apply specifically to the remedy screen and could have a higher impact if the EC defined the elements more precisely, for example:

a) design of switching tools. The EU states that gatekeepers should enable easy switching of default settings on their OS, virtual assistants, and web browsers. However, it does not comment on the specifics of what these switching tools should look like and how many alternative providers users should be able to switch to.

In Google's case, their compliance report mentions that the choice screen was designed using stratified randomization, taking into consideration the European Commission's recommendations to Microsoft in the IE case: “Displaying five browsers in a prominent manner, and seven more when scrolling sideways, strikes an appropriate balance between the

need to have a workable choice screen that users are likely to make use of and making the choice screen as accessible as possible to web browser vendors § (81)”²². However, Google noted that they would transition to complete randomization, following undisclosed feedback from the EC in early 2024 ([Google, 2024, p.128](#)). As of today, it is unclear whether this change will be effective. In [Android.com/choice_screen](#) cited in Google’s report it is still visible, that Google will follow a stratified randomization. Meanwhile, Apple’s compliance report does not show any argumentation regarding the selection of choice screen architecture.

b) Timing of initial choice of screens. § Art. 6(3) mandates an active choice screen for an “first use” of a service by an end user. However, it is not entirely clear what constitutes an “end user’s first use.” Does it refer to: (i) the first time they use the service in question, so pre-existing users are not affected? (ii) the first time they do so after the DMA came into force? (iii) the first time they use (or install) a browser, or virtual assistant on a new device?

From a causal perspective, this is the most relevant unclear point due to the consequences on the scalability of the remedy. Apple and Google address this point differently. Google displays the choice screen only on all new phones (iii), while Apple shows it on all phones after the DMA comes into force (ii).

An approximation on the scalability effect can be measured using data for active mobiles in both OS. In 2023, Apple’s iOS App Store had approximately 101 million users in the EU ([Ceci, 2023](#)), while there were around 318 million active Android users in the EU for the same year ([Taylor, 2024](#)). Studies show that people kept their mobiles for longer periods of time; in 2021 the average mobile replacement cycle in Western Europe was around 40 months²³ a 24% longer than in 2016 ([Duthoit, 2022, p.3](#)). Assuming this cycle length of 40 months, Google’s choice screen will take approximately until July 2027, to be fully implemented across all Android devices, affecting an average of 7 million users monthly²⁴, compared with the 75 million iOS users affected by the choice screen within the first two months of remedy implementation (detailed info in section 3.6 remedy implementation).

²² European Commission, decision of 16.12.2009. – Ref. Case COMP/C-3/39.530 – Microsoft (tying), p.19

²³ As reference in North America the average Mobil replacement is every 24 months.

²⁴ It is reduced around 7% of Android mobiles which has set other browser as default. e. j. Samsung Internet Browser, or Huawei browser.

This extended timeline may not only delay the effectiveness of the remedy but also reduce its overall impact. Smaller browsers, which aim to compete for user's attention and the default position, have an incentive to invest heavily in advertising campaigns during the choice screen period. However, this is not a sustainable strategy for a three-year remedy exposure as shown in the Chrome case.

c) Choice architecture of the initial choice screen. Article 13(6) requires that the gatekeepers cannot present alternatives in a biased way or design the interfaces in a manner that unfairly influences user decisions. Therefore, to make the choice screen more effective, additional guidance on the design of the choice architecture is necessary. For example:

(i) How many options should be included? In the Microsoft browser case, a total of 11 browsers including the incumbent browser, were displayed. In the experiment conducted by [Åkesson et al. \(2023\)](#), two screens were tested: one featuring five browsers and the other displaying twelve. The results showed that 64% of participants preferred the screen with a bigger browser option. In general, the list should be long enough to provide real choice and promote contestability while avoiding choice overload. A number around ten options appear to strike the best balance.

(ii) What order should the options be provided? The approach used in the Microsoft browser case and Google's current choice screen for DMA compliance follows a stratified strategy. While randomization may lead to a poor user experience, especially for users who already know what they want, stratified randomization offers a more reasonable balance. One possible implementation could involve displaying the top five services in random order, followed by the next five in random order.

[Åkesson et al. \(2023\)](#) found that the order in which browsers are presented significantly influences user choices, with effects varying across different browsers. For example, moving from the first to the fourth position reduced Chrome's selection rate by 11%, while Samsung and Edge experienced a 38% drop. This suggests that lower rankings disproportionately harm smaller competitors more. In line with the DMA's "fairness" objective and the EC's recommendations to Google, the research suggestion directs to either implementing and stating a full randomization, or a stratified randomization with the five smaller competitors displayed first and the top five browsers displayed after.

(iii) How much description should be provided? Around 70% of users preferred a choice screen with more information ([Åkesson et al. 2023](#)). Given that end users tend to exhibit "familiarity bias," it would be beneficial to include short descriptions alongside each browser name. This can be a good starting point but developing a comparative framework between browsers could be even more informative for users. For example, the choice screen could display key attributes such as browser security scores, data privacy policies, VPN access, and reward/benefit programs. Summarizing these characteristics would enable users to make more informed decisions aligned with their browser quality perception.

(iv) Should users be reassured that their choice is reversible? Yes, this would help to reduce regret aversion and endowment effects in case the browser does not reach the user's quality threshold.

(v) How frequently will the options list be refreshed? The top 10 browsers have remained fairly constant, meaning that updating the list more frequently may not have the same impact as improving the implementation of the choice screen itself. A review of the list every six months or year should be enough.

Table 2 summarizes the choice architecture elements of the two gatekeepers in the browser market. In general, the elements align with the DMA objectives. However, leaving open definitions such as the implementation timing, could reduce the remedy's effectiveness. In addition, not considering a comparative framework in the browser characteristics adds complexity to users' decision-making, increasing the probability of behavioral biases for example default effect, regret aversion and salient effects.

Tab. 2: Effectiveness questions and gatekeepers' choice architecture

	Apple	Google
End users first use web browser. What's the time interpretation of this?	All Apple mobiles the first time they open the default browser and have at least iOS17.4 (launch 6 March 2024)	All new Android mobiles during setup distributed after 6 March 2024 ²⁵
How many options should be included?	Includes 11 different browsers (Including Safari)	Includes 12 different browsers (Including Chrome)
Which options should be shown?	The 11 most popular browsers in each country the year before	The 12 most popular browsers in each country.
What order should options be provided for?	Completely Random	First the 5 most popular ordered randomly. Then the rest 7 randomly ²⁶
How much description should be provided?	Name and Logo ²⁷	Name, logo and description.
Should users be reassured that their choice is reversible ?	Phrase: "You can change the default browser at any time..." in the choice screen	not reassured phrase in choice screen
How frequently will the option list be refreshed ?	Once a year	Twice a year

Own creation; source of data: Question taken from Fletcher A. in [De Streel et al. \(2023 p.86\)](#). Answered using browser gatekeeper's compliance reports (2024).

3.5 Apple's choice screen

Apple allowed users to change their default browser and default email app after the release of the iOS 14 update on September 16, 2020²⁸. However, the active choice screen was first displayed with the iOS 17.4 update on March 5, 2024. This screen, called "About Your Default Browser" enables users to select their default browser from a list of available options. The choice screen will appear under the following conditions: (i) the user has updated to iOS 17.4, and (ii) Safari is set as the default browser. Figure 1 illustrates the choice screen displayed to EU users who meet these two criteria.

²⁵ Android devices who Chrome is not the default browser for example Samsung mobiles (Samsung internet is the default browser) the choice screen will not appear.

²⁶ Google in their compliance report mentioned that will move from a stratified strategy to a full randomization in the OSEs after EC recommendation [Google, EU DMA Compliance report, App. 34, p. 129, EU DMA Compliance Report]. However, in Android page continue to show that they would use a stratified strategy. <https://www.android.com/choicescreen/dma/browser/>

²⁷ See [Appendix 13.4](#). Apple upcoming update plan is to add a small description of each browser displayed in the choice screen.

²⁸ Apple, About iOS 14 updates. Settings; Option to set your default email and web browser. Online Available at: <https://support.apple.com/en-us/118390> [25/04/2025]

Fig. 1: Screen “About Your Default Browser”

iPhone screen shots, Source of data: iPhone SE, Mobile Set-up project, DICE HHU (2024)

For existing users, the screen will prompt once Safari is opened for the first time after the update. For new users, the screen will appear during the set-up process. The selection process is mandatory and cannot be skipped, requiring users to scroll through the entire list of browser options and choose a default browser to continue. If the selected browser is not installed on the device, the user will be redirected to Apple’s App Store to download the respective browser. Once the download is complete, the newly selected browser will automatically be set as the default.

A detailed description of the screen navigation process is provided in [Appendix Figure B.1](#). For this update²⁹, the browser selection will not affect the design architecture of the home screen. This means that even if another browser is set as the default, the Safari icon will still appear on the main screen. The icon can only be deleted if the user chooses to do it, However Safari can still be found under the menu Apps. This applies to both new and old phones.

²⁹ See [Appendix 13.4](#). In a new update release in 01.12.2024. The default browser elements in the home screen like icons and direct access will be replaced with the default browser selection.

3.6 Remedy implementation

The eleven most downloaded browsers on iOS for each country in the previous year, which meet other Apple developer criteria, will be displayed in the choice screen in addition to Safari, displayed in random order. The criteria and the list of browsers for each of the 27 EU countries can be found on Apple's web page³⁰. The list of browsers is updated once every calendar year and the order in which browsers are displayed in the choice screen is completely random.

The choice screen was introduced with the iOS 17.4 update on March 5, 2024, and is available for iPhone XS models and later³¹. Software updates follow a version number scheme that includes at least one decimal point (e.g., iOS 17.7), while software upgrades use a whole number integer (e.g., iOS 18). When a software update or upgrade becomes available, Apple sends a notification with the OS update number and the option to download or delay it. If the user does not immediately initiate the installation and chooses to delay it, notifications will be sent until the enforcement day on which update cannot be delayed, 30 days after the release of the update.

If the "Do Not Disturb" feature is enabled, notifications will be suspended until 24 hours prior to the enforcement date. The visual notification calendar process is detailed in [Appendix Figure B.2](#). To enforce the installation of an update, upgrade, or Rapid Security Response, a device must meet the same requirements as those for a user-initiated update of the same type³². Thus it can be deduced that iOS devices that have not updated to iOS 17.4 within one month after its release do not comply with the updating requirements and, therefore, will not encounter the remedy screen.

³⁰ [About the browser choice screen in the EU - Support - Apple Developer](#) [19.11.2024]

³¹ As reference iPhone XS went on sale 21.09.2018. <https://support.apple.com/en-us/100100> [23.11.2024]

³² Requirements necessary; Internet network, power requirement, space requirements and term and conditions. More detailed explanation available online in <https://support.apple.com/guide/deployment/about-software-updates-depc4c80847a/web> [10.09.2024]

The update process is critical to this analysis, as the display of the treatment screen depends on the adoption rate of iOS 17.4. The evolution of the update system, illustrated in Figure 2, demonstrates that the most significant adoption rate and thus the highest likelihood of encountering the treatment screen— did not occur upon the release of iOS 17.4 on March 5, 2024, but rather one month later, following the enforcement date.

Fig. 2: Adoption rate of iOS17.4

Own creation; source of data: Statista (2024), iOS version. Past version values contain the sum of all other versions before iOS 17.4 update..

[Appendix Table A.3](#) provides a list of all EU countries treated with their respective adoption rate of iOS 17.4. It is observed that the adoption rates were similar across all countries, with the exception of Lithuania, which was marked as an outlier and excluded from the analysis. In the week following the enforcement date, the adoption rate surged by 46%, indicating that approximately one of every two iPhones within the EU were treated with the choice screen during that week.

4. Quantitative analysis

To investigate the effect of the “About your default browser” choice screen, a series of descriptive and empirical analyses were conducted and are explained in the following chapter. [Subchapter 4.1](#) provides an explanation of the data used for the analysis. [Subchapter 4.2](#) focuses on browser downloads, beginning with descriptive statistics before and after the remedy implementation, followed by an empirical analysis of the remedy’s impact. [Subchapter 4.3](#) looks at browser usage descriptives, which sets the basis for the causal analysis.

4.1 Data

The data on browser market share for iOS mobiles and iOS version, was obtained from StatCounter, a traffic analysis service that records more than 5 billion page views each month across over 1,5 million global websites, with approximately half originating from mobile devices. StatCounter tracks various metrics including country, browser, search engine, OS, device vendor, screen resolution, OS version and even social media usage³³.

The browser market share data was collected at a daily frequency from October 1, 2023, to September 30, 2024, covering 52 countries, resulting in a total of 18.668 observations. During this period, 34 browsers were registered³⁴. Additionally, monthly frequency data was collected from January 2009 to October 2024 for the same 52 countries. For iOS systems, data was collected for the 27 treated countries over a 90-day window—45 days before and 45 days after the release of iOS 17.4.

Data regarding browser downloads was sourced from AppTweak, an app store optimization tool that estimates daily downloads across 70 countries. The dataset includes daily downloads for the 10 most popular browsers on the Apple App Store, segmented by device type: iPhone (mobiles), iPad (tablets), and Android mobiles via the Google Play Store. The sample covers 27 countries treated from October 1, 2022, to September 30, 2024, yielding 18.927 observations for each app store format.

³³ StatCounter base their stats on page views (and not unique visitors). This means they consider multi-browser usage (multihoming) by individuals. <https://gs.statcounter.com/factsheet> [03.10.2024]

³⁴ StatCounter doesn’t register individually the share of browser extremely small, but the summary of their market shares, which is stated as “others” and included in our analysis.

4.2 Browser Downloads

The remedy effect analysis begins by examining the total number of browser downloads on the “Release”, “Enforcement” and “Maximum number of downloads” days in the 26 treated countries³⁵, comparing it with the average number of downloads before treatment. As a reminder, Safari is not included in this analysis, because Safari is preinstalled on all iOS systems and doesn't require a separate download.

Tab. 3: EU Browser downloads

	Average	Treatment 6.03.2024	$\Delta\%$ Avg vs treat	Enforcement 7.04.2024	$\Delta\%$ Avg vs Enfor	Max Downloads 10.04.2024	$\Delta\%$ Avg vs Max
Chrome	25014	82726	231%	99581	298%	103354	313%
Edge	6862	13424	96%	20909	205%	38488	461%
Firefox	2705	13560	401%	23791	780%	54965	1932%
Opera	2444	8697	256%	7377	202%	13586	456%
Brave	2884	5589	94%	5906	105%	9030	213%
DuckDuckGo	1121	5087	354%	6238	456%	12722	1035%
Ecosia	310	2848	819%	5634	1717%	13060	4113%
Aloha	290	702	142%	974	236%	2037	602%
Yandex	170	550	224%	741	336%	1293	661%
You.com	120	208	73%	560	367%	1230	925%
Total	41920	133391	218%	171711	310%	249765	496%

Own creation; Source of data: AppTweak (2024). Average column represent the average iOS mobile browser downloads in April 2023. 10.04.2024 add it as the day with more browser downloads registered in mobile iOS. Browser table account for <98% of total browser available for mobiles iOS

Table 3 shows the descriptive analysis for the most important browsers available in mobile App Stores within EU countries. The $\Delta\%$ columns highlight the change relative to pre-treatment average values. Meanwhile, Figure 3 shows the daily downloads for each browser over a period of 18 months pre-treatment and 6 months post-treatment.

On the day of treatment release, total browser downloads increased 218% vs the average. All browsers experience extraordinary numbers of downloads thanks to treatment, with Ecosia experiencing growth rates of 800% due to its initially low average number of downloads. However, in absolute terms, Google benefited the most from the choice screen implementation, accounting for 57.712 additional downloads, approximately 63% of the total increase. As a result, Google gained 3.33% in downloads market share compared to its average market share.

³⁵ Lithuania set as outlier and was left out of the analysis.

On the enforcement day, total browser downloads increased by 129.791 compared to the baseline average, marking a 310% surge. All browsers except Opera experience a higher growth than on their treatment day, with Firefox showing an increase close to 800% and Ecosia growing 1700%. Notably, Firefox continued its upward trend in the number of downloads, reaching its peak on April 10, 2024, the day with the highest number of browser downloads with nearly 55.000 downloads, accounting for 22% of all downloads that day. Despite this surge, Google Chrome still dominated the market, capturing 74.567 of the additional downloads on the enforcement day, representing 57,54% of the choice screen effect, but unlike the treatment day, losing 2,13% in terms of market share.

Fig. 3: EU mobile iOS browser downloads.

Own creation; Source of data: AppTweak (2024), Mobile iOS browser downloads. Dotted line represents treatment release day 05.04.2024. Solid line represents enforcement day 06.05.2024.

To assess the long-term impact of the remedy, market shares were plotted and regressed against the treatment. The average of the browsers were calculated, accounting for over 98% of the total browser downloads. Then market shares are presented in the following way:

$$S_{bt} = \frac{q_{bt}}{\sum_{i \in M} q_{it}} \quad (1)$$

Where q_{bt} represent the downloads for a browser (b) on a given day (t), while $\sum_{i \in M} q_{it}$ denotes the total downloads for all 10 browsers (i) on the same day.

The evolution of market shares over time is depicted in Figure 4, where the impact on the enforcement day is more evident than on the release day, particularly benefiting smaller browsers, specifically Firefox. This impact seems to dissipate in the following days, with market share returning to pre-remedy levels. In August 2024, four months after the release of the remedy, a change in the trend of some browsers can be seen. However, the period in between shows no visible evidence of a sustained treatment effect that suggest the later trend shift was caused by the remedy.

Fig. 4: Market share EU mobile iOS browser downloads

Own creation; Sources data: AppTweak (2024), Browser market share values using formula (1). Dotted line represents treatment release day 05.04.2024. Solid line represents enforcement day 06.05.2024.

To test for treatment effects in the long run of browser downloads, regression 2 is run for each browser. The analysis also identified a weekly seasonality pattern, with higher browser downloads occurring on weekends. Additionally, a Dickey-Fuller (DF) test for stationarity found no significant trends in the data, meaning the coefficient of interest β_{bi} is robust in accounting for the treatment effect. Formally regression is presented

$$Market_Share_Down_{it} = \alpha + \beta_{bi}Treat_{ct} + \lambda_c + \sum \gamma_d Weekday_{it} + \varepsilon_{ct} \quad (2)$$

Where $Treatment_{ct}$ is a dummy variable = 1 if observation is treated, λ_c account for Country fix effects, and $\sum \gamma_d Weekday_{it}$ is a set of dummies for each day of the week. The results, presented in Table 4, show that after correcting for autocorrelation, all treatment coefficients are statistically significant at the 1% level.

Table 4. Estimated change in EU market share of downloads due to treatment

	Chrome	Edge	Opera	Brave	Firefox	Ecosia	DuckDuckGo	Aloha	Yandex	You.com
Post treatment Effect	0.02050*** (0.002836)	-0.03020*** (0.002172)	0.01719*** (0.001899)	-0.01340*** (0.000680)	0.00278*** (0.000929)	0.00318*** (0.000253)	0.00171*** (0.000402)	0.00052*** (0.000079)	-0.00254*** (0.000145)	-0.00356*** (0.00045)
Country FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Adj. R2	0.65591	0.65164	0.40155	0.3159	0.49892	0.45705	0.50146	0.14436	0.65487	0.08646
Within R2	0.10316	0.26465	0.09567	0.1532	0.00786	0.04964	0.03416	0.00873	0.04504	0.03621
Average Market Share	0.64173	0.15359	0.03831	0.06422	0.05761	0.00379	0.02749	0.00419	0.00813	0.00603
Observations	16123	14276	16123	16123	16123	16123	16123	16123	13642	6925

Own creation; Source of data: AppTweak (2024). Country FE and weekday controls. Standard error NW adjusted with lag(1)

Chrome benefited the most from the treatment, gaining an average of 2% market share in downloads, followed by Opera with a 1.7% increase. Despite Firefox’s substantial gains on the treatment day, its average market share increase remained below 1%. The most significant decline was observed for Edge, which lost 3% of its market share in downloads. For smaller browsers, the treatment yielded mixed results: Ecosia doubled its market share in downloads (though it remained below 1%), while Yandex and You experienced significant declines relative to their average market share.

Overall, the treatment had a relatively minor impact on Browser downloads in iPhones, with gains and losses not exceeding 2.5%. Given that users could have reverted the default browsers decision or engaged in multi-homing, a broader browser usage analysis—including Safari—is necessary to assess the remedy’s true effectiveness

4.3 Browser Use

For the second part of the pattern analysis, browser market share usage on iOS mobile systems is evaluated. Unlike the downloads analysis, this sample includes a larger set of countries divided into treatment and control groups. A total of 52 countries were analyzed, with 26 EU countries (excluding Lithuania) forming the treatment group and the remaining 26 countries, comprising non-treated European countries and OECD countries members, serving as the control group. Table 5 presents the average browser usage distribution. Safari and Chrome together account for approximately 90% of the market share, clear evidence in their market relevance and further designation as gatekeepers.

Tab. 5: Browser market share usage

	Control Group			Treatment Group		
	Before	After	Δ%	Before	After	Δ%
Safari	35.33844	32.93932	-7%	28.35724	25.91759	-9%
Chrome	55.67230	57.73599	4%	61.98818	63.85796	3%
Edge	0.25379	0.32309	27%	0.22755	0.29964	32%
Firefox	0.58722	0.62455	6%	0.79882	0.98462	23%
Opera	0.39796	0.21846	-45%	1.12771	1.16308	3%
DuckDuckGo	0.01835	0.04423	141%	0.01331	0.01615	21%
Ecosia	0.04392	0.06489	48%	0.07260	0.09836	35%
Yandex	0.26814	0.30915	15%	0.10813	0.12675	17%
Total	92.58012	92.25968	0.35%	92.69355	92.46415	0.25%

Own Creation; Source of data: Statista (2024), Browser market share. Period from 1.10.2023 to 30.09.2024. Breaking point treatment 5.05.2024.

The market shares studied cover 92% of the total mobile browser traffic³⁶. Chrome is the dominant browser in most countries, with a slightly higher market concentration in the treated group (EU countries) compared to the control group. In fact, in all treated countries except Sweden and Norway, Chrome is the most-used browser. In the control group, Safari has a stronger presence leading in the following countries Albania, Andorra, Australia, Canada, Monaco, Switzerland, and the United States.

The first comparative results indicate a negative trend in Safari usage before and after the treatment, with a slightly more pronounced decline in the treatment group. This reduction in market share appears to be captured primarily by Chrome, which shows an average increase in both countries' samples. In both groups, all browsers exhibit market share gains over time,

³⁶ Samsung Internet, the default browser for Samsung phones, accounts for about 5% of the total browser market share, but is not included in the analysis because it is not available for iOS systems.

except for Opera in the control group. The comparative market share results suggest that the treatment may have influenced consumer behavior differently in treated countries compared to the control group.

A visual analysis of browser market share trends provides further insights into usage patterns. Figure 5 illustrates the evolution of the market share for Chrome and Safari over time, comparing the treatment and control group. The trends exhibit similar trajectories before and after the treatment. From October 2023 to June 2024, Safari's market share shows a consistent decline, while Chrome appears to absorb these losses, indicating a substitution effect.

Following the implementation of the remedy, no clear (visual) evidence of long-term effects can be detected. In the short term, immediately after the enforcement date, a noticeable decline in Safari's market share is observed, accompanied by an increase in Chrome's market share. This shift lasts for approximately one week before the trends revert to previous levels. This pattern persists until June 2024, when the market share trends for both browsers stabilize. However, by the end of September 2024, a turning point occurs, and Safari recovers approximately 2% of its market share, returning to levels comparable to the previous year and reversing losses sustained during late 2023 and early 2024.

Own creation; source of data: Statista (2024), Market Shares. Dotted line represents treatment release day 05.04.2024. Solid line represents enforcement day 06.05.2024.

Moving into the visual analysis of other browser competitors, Figure 6 shows the average market share of the remaining browsers. For a better readability the control group values were not included. A similar trend to Figure 5 is observed in the short run for treatment and enforcement days. However, this positive shock seems to be within the normal variation of the market share. Firefox seems to shift its tendency after the enforcement day. Meanwhile, the variance of Edge increases after the same period. In the case of Opera and Ecosia, there is no visual impact.

Fig. 6: Other browsers market share in the treatment group.

Own creation; source of data: Statista (2024), Market Shares. Dotted line represents treatment release day 05.04.2024. Solid line represents enforcement day 06.05.2024.

5. Causal results

Chapter 5 presents the main and novel results from this paper, beginning with [Subchapter 5.1](#), where the causal DiD model and its variations are introduced. [Subchapter 5.2](#) presents the initial results, starting with a more detailed analysis of Safari estimates, followed by all other browsers. Furthermore this section examines the estimates over time in relation to the remedy's release. [Subchapter 5.3](#) presents the event study estimates, assessing whether heterogeneity exists depending on the timing on which the remedy was displayed. [Subchapter 5.4](#) explores heterogeneity driven by geographical factors, specifically across countries. Finally, [Subchapter 5.5](#) presents the estimates using different standard errors clustering techniques, serving as a robustness check for the significance of the main findings.

5.1 Model Identification

The causal analysis of the remedy is conducted using a difference-in-differences (DiD) model, starting with Safari. Based on the observed data patterns, it is expected to find a statistically significant decrease in Safari's market share usage, as well as a statistically significant increase in the market share usage of other browsers. Among these browsers, Chrome is expected to benefit the most from the treatment, in line with the trends observed in the browser download data and market share shifts post-treatment. The DiD strategy allows isolating the effect of the remedy by comparing changes over time and between groups.

The DiD model holds the following assumptions: SUTVA, no anticipation effect, orthogonality of treatment assignment and parallel trends. These assumptions are explained and tested in [Appendix C](#). For the DiD analysis, two different control group samples are used. The "Europe" sample which consist 14 EEA countries that were not treated and the "Europe + OECD" sample which consists of the same 14 EEA countries plus 12 OECD countries that were not treated, forming a control group of 26 countries. The regression specification is applied in two ways: first, using the absolute market share values and second using a weighted sample, where countries are weighted by their mobile cellular subscriptions as a proxy for user market size. The list of treated countries, the two control group samples, and the mobile cellular subscription data by country can be found in [Appendix Table A.2](#).

In the regression analysis, both daily fixed and country fixed effects are included to control for any unobserved time-specific or country-specific factors that might influence the results. The model is run for the treatment day and extended to account for non-binary and non-absorbing treatment, considering the intensity of iOS adoption between the treatment and enforcement days. The robustness section allows for heteroskedasticity and corrects for autocorrelation. The main DiD model is specified as:

$$Y_{bit} = \alpha + \beta_k(Post_t \times Treat_i) + \lambda_c + \gamma_t + \varepsilon_{bct} \quad (3)$$

Where Y_{bit} is the market share of browser (b) in country (i) in day (t), λ_c is a country fixed effect, γ_t is a daily fixed effect, and $Post_t \times Treat_i$ is the DiD variable that equals to 1 for treated countries after remedy is implemented, or is 0 otherwise. β_k represents the treatment effect, the variable of interest.

In the model, possible heterogeneity in the treatment effect is considered by calculating event-study estimators ([De Chaisemartin & d'Haultfoeuille, 2024](#)), which allows the examination of whether the marginal treatment effect varies with respect to the time at which the treatment was displayed. Since treatment exposure increases over time in a non-linear manner (due to iOS 17.4 adoption), the values are normalized and interacted in the DiD model with dummy variables representing the day order with respect to the reference day, set as -1 or one day before treatment. The explained method extends the DiD model regression to:

$$Y_{bit} = \alpha + \sum_{k \neq -1} \beta_k \times 1\{r = k\} \times D_{it} + \lambda_c + \gamma_t + \varepsilon_{bct} \quad (4)$$

Where Y_{bit} , λ_c , γ_t follows the definition of model (3). The indicator $1\{r = k\}$ equals 1 if the day is k periods relative to treatment (with $r = -1$ omitted as the baseline). D_{it} represent the normalized adoption rate of the iOS 17.4 or treatment exposure (before a dummy variable, now continuous). The coefficient β_k represents the additional effect on the browser market share per unit of the normalized adoption rate at event time K, compared with the pre-treatment values.

5.2 Difference in differences

Table 6 presents the results of the DiD model (3) for Safari across different control groups and sample specifications. As observed, the expected negative impact is evident in three out of the five regression specifications. However, in the model that captures the most variation (Specification 4), the treatment effect is positive. In none of the five specifications the treatment effect is statistically significant, indicating that the remedy does not have a measurable impact on Safari's use market share. After controlling for daily and country fixed effects, the model explains more than 97% of the sample variation. The results remain robust across different standard errors clustering specifications.

Tab. 6: DiD estimators Safari browser

	(1) Safari	(2) Safari	(3) Safari	(4) Safari	(5) Safari
Sample	Europe	Europe Weighted	Europe + OECD	European + OECD Weighted	European + OECD Weighted
Treated x Post	-0.940359 (1.30724)	-1.08038 (1.38412)	-0.036117 (1.13531)	0.128404 (1.33789)	0.128404 (1.32482)
Treated					-12.767341 * (6.72187)
post5marz					-3.296418 ** (1.06421)
Daily & Country FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
R-squared Adj	0.940609	0.959106	0.94623	0.976657	0.145782
Observations	14274	14274	18666	18666	18666

Own creation; Source of data, Statista (2024). Standard-errors clustered by country and show in parenthesis

The same DiD model regression is applied to all other browsers, the results can be found in [Appendix Tables A.4](#). A summary of all browsers for the DiD model that captures more of the variation; regression (4) "European + OECD Weighted" is presented in Table 7, alongside with the pre-remedy market share. As a robustness check, the Samsung Internet Browser (which is not available for iOS) is included in the analysis. As expected, the treatment effect is not significant for this browser.

Tab. 7: DiD estimators all browsers

	(1) Safari	(2) Chrome	(3) Firefox	(4) Opera	(5) Edge	(6) Ecosia	(7) Samsung
Treated x Post	0.128404 (1.33789)	-0.693007 (1.29117)	0.160511 * (0.087215)	0.174672 *** (0.038731)	-0.046764 (0.035667)	0.063783 ** (0.019901)	0.15754 (.103704)
Daily and Country FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
R-Squared Adj	0.976657	0.976703	0.841294	0.950787	0.63747	0.882038	0.991441
Observations	18666	18666	18666	18666	18666	14364	18666
Pre Remedy Share	33.607	57.112	0.627	0.608	0.295	0.055	4.825

Own creation; Source of data; Statista (2024) Standard errors clustered by country and show in

Similar to Safari, the treatment effect for Google Chrome is not statistically significant. Moreover, the observed impact is negative, contrary to the expected positive effect. However, smaller browsers—Firefox, Opera, and Ecosia—exhibit statistically significant market share gains in line with the anticipated effects of the remedy. The combined increase in market share for these three browsers accounts for 0,39% of the total market share. These gains come at the expense of Safari’s losses; however, the differential is so small relative to Safari’s natural fluctuations that is not statistically distinguished from its own variation or negative pre-treatment trend. Among the browsers for which the treatment effect is significant, Firefox grows by 25%, Opera by 29%, and Ecosia doubles its market share, increasing by 115%. This substantial percentage increase for Ecosia is largely due to its small initial market share of only 0,055%.

The intended objective of the DMA to foster a more competitive market appears to be on the right track, benefiting smaller competitors. However, the overall variation and treatment effect remain significantly small when considering the sum of market share values of Safari and Chrome higher than 90%. These findings align with those of [Decarolis et al. \(2024\)](#), who conclude that mobile users exhibit inertia and status quo bias. Being the default option, whether as search engine or, in this case as browser, remains highly valuable for providers. The results suggest that merely minimizing switching costs has a limited effect on market shares.

Figure 7 displays the daily DiD estimate coefficients for regression type (4), excluding daily fixed effects due to collinearity issues with the day dummies. The coefficients and their significance are measured relative to the day before treatment (t-1). As observed, Safari’s market share appears to be only slightly impacted on average, with no statistically significant changes following the treatment release. The blue line in the figures marks the enforcement

date period, during which Safari's market share experiences a more noticeable decline, likely due to the increased exposure to the treatment. However, this decline gradually reverts to pre-treatment values, indicating that the treatment effect does not persist over time.

Fig. 7: Timeline DiD Estimators for Safari and Chrome

Own creation. Source of data; Statista (2024). Blue line represents 31 periods after treatment release (enforcement day). 95% Confidence interval

The Chrome coefficient reflects the opposite pattern and confirms the complementary relationship between these browsers. On the first day post-treatment, a positive but not statistically significant impact is observed. After enforcement, a positive shift in the Chrome coefficients is noted, but once again, the changes are not statistically significant compared to the day before treatment. Furthermore, the impact appears to dissipate, with Chrome's market share returning to pre-treatment levels.

The same analysis was conducted for the remaining browsers, with graphs provided in [Appendix Figure B.3](#). For the cases of Opera, Firefox, and Ecosia, the graphs indicate statistically significant changes following the treatment and enforcement implementation. However, there is no evidence of changes in the tendency indicating long-term or permanent effects on browser usage. In general, the coefficients for these browsers are close to zero, suggesting that while there were short-term impacts, the average effects do not align with intended long-term outcomes. This implies that the remedy's effect on market share for these smaller browsers may be temporary, with no lasting shift in consumer behavior.

5.3 Event study estimators

The event-study estimators will provide valuable insights into knowing whether consumers who "rapidly" update their OS to the latest version available, react differently than those who are "mandated" to update their software after some time. This distinction can serve as a proxy for user attention. The reasoning behind this is that users who update their phones first are likely to make more conscious decisions, whereas consumers who delay the software update may be less engaged with the update content and more focused on maintaining their existing configurations, including their default browser.

If this assumption holds, the expected relationship between the treatment effect and the marginal adoption rate will be stronger and statistically different from zero in the initial days after the treatment, as these early adopters are more likely to be attuned to changes. For the following days, the effect should level out, and for the post-enforcement period, the event-study estimators should not experience any variation compared to the pre-enforcement estimators. If this is not the case, it implies that user engagement and treatment effect vary with other variables and not related to user attention.

Fig. 8: Event study estimators, heterogeneous treatment effect

Own creation; source of data: Statista & AppTweak (2024). Solid line represent 31 periods after treatment release (enforcement day). 95% Confidence interval.

Figure 8 illustrates the cases of Firefox and Opera, the browsers that exhibit the most significant treatment effects³⁷. Consistent with the user attention hypothesis, both browsers show a notable variation at the beginning of the treatment, which levels out over time. However, the only period where a significant difference indicates heterogeneous behavior is the fourth day after treatment for Opera browser. For all other periods across both browsers, there is no evidence of a significant heterogeneous effect accounting for the adoption rate.

From these results, it can be concluded that user attention does play a role in the treatment effect, but it does not appear to be substantial enough to produce statistically significant

³⁷ Other browser event study estimators' graphs in [Appendix Figure B.4](#)

results. Both early adopters who update their OS voluntarily, and later adopters who update their phones once mandated, seem to react similarly to the treatment. This suggests that user attention towards the treatment is relevant but not a dominant factor in determining the overall effect of the remedy.

5.4 Country heterogeneity

To examine whether the treatment effect varies across countries, particularly concerning local adoption, an interaction term with the “country” variable is added to our (3) DiD regression.

$$Y_{bit} = \alpha + \beta_v(Post_t \times Treat_i \times Country_v) + \lambda_c + \gamma_t + \varepsilon_{bct} \quad (5)$$

This modification results in a vector of coefficients β_v , where each entry of the vector represents a country specific treatment effect. Regression (5) is estimated using the control sample of the European and OECD countries, weighted by the number of mobile subscriptions.

Figure 9 presents the graphs of Safari as the studied default browser, and Opera the browser with the largest treatment impact³⁸. For Safari, the treatment is statistically significant and follows the expected negative effect for Ireland, Denmark, Czechia, and Finland. For Ireland and Czechia, Chrome has a high market share. In Denmark, where Safari was the market leader before the treatment the negative effect is reversed, and Safari lost this position to Chrome after the policy intervention.

³⁸ Country heterogeneity graphs for other browsers can be found in [Appendix Figure B.5](#).

Fig. 9: DiD estimators by country

Own creation; Source of data: Statista (2024). 99% Confidence Interval. DiD incorporating country and day fixed effects

For countries with the largest user bases within the treated countries, Germany and France, the remedy appears to have a negative effect; however, the impact is not statistically different from zero. In contrast, Greece, Cyprus, and Bulgaria exhibit significant positive treatment effects, suggesting that the treatment led to unexpected outcomes. For Opera, the effect is more straightforward, with statistically significant market share gains in 19 out of the 26 countries treated.

For the remaining browsers, shown in [Appendix Figure A.3](#), Chrome exhibits their complementarity with Safari, gaining significant market share in Ireland, Denmark, Czechia, and Finland. Firefox demonstrates strong local adoption in certain countries, particularly

Italy, Austria, and Germany (countries with a high user base) where the treatment effect exceeds 0,2%. Edge does not gain market share in any country except Luxembourg, while Ecosia shows strong local adoption in Germany, France, Belgium and Austria.

To explain the heterogeneity in the results, it is necessary to set a browser demand model (see [Appendix E](#)). The model was taken from [Allcott et al. \(2025\)](#) and adapted to the browser case where user election is a utility maximization problem, function of the default browser quality and the quality beliefs of alternative browsers. Within browser quality the model introduces the observable characteristics for browser performance and their additional service, such as VPN, cashback, security scores, speed and stability and battery performance ([Li, 2023](#)). The demand model accounts for consumer naivety about browser quality, switching costs and inattention. It also explains heterogeneity and illustrates four hypotheses why Safari was not affected by the remedy. (i) the quality of Safari is generally better than browser alternatives, (ii) consumers perceive the quality of browser alternatives to be worse than it actually is (iii) the switching costs from the default Safari are high and (iv) Safari's fraction of inattentive users is large. These reasons are not mutually exclusive, and the estimation of the demand coefficients is necessary to test each hypothesis.

Based on this paper results (i) Safari would not be the browser with the best quality if quality is based on network effects. Safari is characterized by high security scores and high governance but being the browser with the highest quality is discussible and beyond this paper's objectives. (ii) the choice screen does not tackle consumer beliefs about alternatives. (iii) the choice screen remedy reduces the effect of switching costs, the effect observed in market shares is primarily the switching cost impact, and (iv) the proxy event study estimators show no evidence of inattentive / attentive users behaving differently due to choice screen; however it does not say anything about these users type size. The optimal choice and thus the goal of the remedy would be that consumers learn the true browser quality for all alternatives and make active choices without switching costs.

5.5 Robustness

The robustness section focuses on the standard errors associated with the remedy effect. The baseline analysis for the regression (3) reports standard errors clustered at country level. However, this methodology has been criticized by [Bertrand et al \(2004\)](#), who argue that DiD estimation may suffer from error autocorrelation issues. To address these concerns, Table 8 reports confidence intervals using different clustering techniques. The analysis begins with (i) clustering by “country” as baseline. (ii) Two-way clustering at “country” and “date” levels, (iii) Newey-West standard errors which account for serial correlation, and (iv) Driscoll-Kraay standard errors, which correct for both serial (time) and cross-sectional (country) correlation.

Tab. 8: Standard Errors with Various Clustering Techniques

DiD coefficient	Safari			Chrome			Firefox			Opera			Edge			Ecosia		
	Lower Bound	95%	Upper Bound															
	0.128404			-0.693007			0.160511			0.174672			-0.046764			0.063783		
Baseline (Country)	-2.55883	-	2.81564	-3.28639	-	1.90038	-0.01467	*	0.33569	0.09688	***	0.25247	-0.11840	-	0.02487	0.02365	**	0.10392
Two-ways (Country + Date)	-2.53440	-	2.79121	-3.26186	-	1.87585	-0.01309	*	0.33411	0.09692	***	0.25242	-0.11754	-	0.02401	0.02328	**	0.10429
Newey West (NW)	-0.34717	-	0.60398	-1.16062	**	-0.22539	0.12481	***	0.19621	0.14525	***	0.20410	-0.06490	***	-0.02863	0.05186	***	0.07570
Discoll-Kraay (DK)	-0.38603	-	0.64284	-1.17710	**	-0.20892	0.12214	***	0.19889	0.13935	***	0.21000	-0.06135	***	-0.03218	0.04237	***	0.08520

****.001 ***.01 **.1

*Own creation; Source of data: Statista (2024). 95% Confidence interval, “****”.001 “***”.01 “**”.1 Significant market in 95% column.*

Safari is the only browser that does not show statistical significance under any standard error technique, reinforcing the robustness of the null effect of the treatment on Safari's market share. For Chrome, the coefficient becomes significant when autocorrelation in errors is considered, but in the opposite direction of the expected impact. The confidence intervals then indicate a significant negative effect, suggesting that Chrome may have lost up to 1% of its market share due to the treatment.

Similarly, for Edge, when time-based autocorrelation is considered, the coefficient becomes significant at the 95% confidence level, indicating a loss of approximately 0,04% in market share after the treatment. In contrast, the results for Firefox, Opera, and Ecosia remain robust across all clustering techniques, consistently showing statistical significance.

6. Discussion

Recalling the two research questions (1) *What is the effect of Apple's implementation of the 'About Your Default Browser' choice screen on downloads and market share of iOS mobile browsers?* And (2) *What evidence-based modifications could be implemented to achieve a fairer and more contestable remedy in the browser market?*, the results can be summarized and discussed as followed:

(1) Among the choice architecture elements implemented by Apple, the remedy effect is a general increase and higher variance in the total number of iOS mobile browser downloads. Extraordinary increases occurred on the release and enforcement days of the iOS17.4 update. On these specific days, smaller browsers benefited the most, experiencing triple-digit growth and gaining market share relative to the market leader. In the long term, however, the effect does not follow the same pattern. The remedy ultimately led to an overall increase of 2% in Chrome downloads – the highest of any browser - followed by Opera, which saw a 1.7% increase. Conversely, the browsers that saw the biggest drop in downloads were Microsoft Edge (-3%) and Brave (-1.34%).

Regarding browser usage For the two dominant browsers, Safari and Chrome, which together control more than 90% of the mobile market in the EU, the treatment shows no sustainable impact on their respective market shares. These results were robust across different sample compositions and diverge from the expected outcome in different ways.

For the default browser Safari, the treatment was expected to diminish usage due to the reduction of switching costs and the requirement for users to make an explicit choice, leading to a revealed preference for alternative browsers. However, after the treatment implementation, the observed impact on Safari usage was minimal and statistically indistinguishable from zero, the overall trend usage remained unaffected, suggesting that the treatment did not causally influence the variation in Safari's market share.

For Chrome, the browser with the highest market share, the expected outcome was an increase in usage given Chrome's strong quality perception bias. The assumption was that Chrome would capture the largest share of users switching away from Safari, with the relationship $\Delta\text{Chrome} < \Delta\text{SumBrowser} < \Delta\text{SafariLosses}$. However, after treatment

implementation, the observed impact on Chrome usage was not significantly different from zero. In the robustness checks, the effect was in opposite to the initial expectation, with a slight loss of market share for Chrome.

For Microsoft Edge, similar to Safari, there was no statistically significant change in market share after the treatment. On the other hand, Firefox, Opera and Ecosia were the only browsers affected by the remedy, gaining a combined 0,37% of market share. Ecosia and Firefox showed a higher local adoption in specific countries, whereas Opera showed a significant treatment effect in all countries, but with less variance in local adoption.

The findings of the limited effectiveness of the choice screen remedy are consistent with the results of [Decarolis et al. \(2024\)](#). They measure the impact of the choice screen for selecting the default search engine, which was only implemented for new Android phones within EU, where the treatment effect was estimated to be less than 2%. Using the results they run a counterfactual in the case that the screen would be displayed to all Android users within the EU. Counterfactual results showed a 3%-point drop for Google's search engine, passing from 98% to 95% of the search engine market.

Interestingly, the remedy effect is heterogeneous with respect to the degree of market share concentration. In the case of Russian search engines, In 2017 Google have the default position in Android phones and accounted for around 70%, while Yandex's market share was around 30%. The Russia Federal Antimonopoly service (FAS) required Google to take a series of actions to restore competition³⁹, including a choice screen implementation. The choice screen appeared in April 2017, showing only three search engines – Google, Yandex and Mail.ru. Google's market share dropped between 7.8% and 12.2% due to the treatment effect and in July 2019, Yandex and Google shared the market almost equally.

The effect of choice screen remedies in concentrated markets is limited. Although the choice screens may reduce certain forms of friction, e.g. switching costs (iii), they do not eliminate the larger barrier to competition that exists; user's naivety about the quality of competing

³⁹ (i) remove the exclusivity of Google applications on android devices in Russia, (ii) stop restricting the pre-installation of competing search engines and applications (iii) stop enforcing the clauses in its previously signed settlement contract (iv) ensure the rights of third-party search engines to be included into the choice window.

alternatives (ii) [Allcott et al. \(2025\)](#). This affects principally smaller size competitors who don't benefit from network market effects. Moreover, the persuasion literature has documented that for a message to be successful people must have the interest and the ability to process it (iv). Only under the assumption that people have the interest to consider an alternative and account with complete information regarding the available options the choice screen is necessary [Duque \(2024\)](#).

(2) About possible modifications to achieve a fairer and more contestable market in the core browser platform, the answer can be divided into (i) what modifications can be made to the choice architecture of the choice screen and (ii) which strategy modifications can be implemented instead of or in addition to the choice screen.

Regarding choice architecture (i), the literature review in the analysis of the DMA articles reveals a lack of clear definition in terms of concepts and specifications that the choice screen should include. This leads to differences in how the choice architecture is implemented by gatekeepers in the core browser platform. For example, Google's interpretation of "first-time users" as stated in Article 6(3) of the DMA, is that the choice screen should appear the first time an Android phone is set up. Under this interpretation, it could take up to three years for the choice screen to be displayed to all Android users, given the average time duration between device replacements. This interpretation has negative consequences, such as weakening the impact of the remedy and reducing the effectiveness of the investments made by browsers to capture user attention and increase brand awareness during the choice screen decision process.

The Apple choice screen architecture changes implemented in iOS18.2 are relevant modifications that will allow consumers to make better informed decisions, such as the addition of a description below each browser and a link to review each browser's App Store product page. Moreover, the User Experience (UX) to change the default browser was improved related to the choice screen in iOS 17.4, meaning a reduction on the switching costs and facilitating the adoption of the new default browser. A full explanation and screenshots of the modified screens can be found in [Appendix D](#).

Regarding the other elements for the choice architecture the actual literature and past evidence in the Microsoft case⁴⁰ ([Åkesson et al. \(2023\)](#), [Fletcher et al., 2024.](#)) aligns with the recommended elements shown in the Apple choice screen. However, the effectiveness of the new choice architecture can be improved if it is accounted that default lasts for an endowment effect. A comparative framework within the choice screen, together with the description can lead to a more informed decision. For example, showing browser security scores, browser data policy, browser extra services like VPN access, and browser reward and benefits. Due to choice fatigue and user attention, the best way that can be presented is summarizing or ranking the available options.

The idea of creating a comparative framework may bias the user's decisions, contrary to the objectives of the DMA. Then the summary, ranking or selected strategy should respect the same principles on which the DMA is based, it should be designed in a fair manner and consider behavioral techniques avoiding self-preference, steering, ranking bias (other than the ranked characteristic) and salient effect. A topic for further research is the possibility to design the most efficient choice architecture in terms of UI and UX, based on the actual screen and the marginal effect of the changes introduced in the iOS18.2 update.

Regarding (ii), the strategy modifications that can be implemented instead or additionally to the choice screen, it is discussed using the evidence in the literature, that choice screens may not be the most effective way to control default in digital markets. There is an implicit premise in the choice screen debate that the goal of forced choices is to (i) provide information to the users and (ii) prompt a decision to ensure that they reveal their actual preference.

Different alternatives to deal with default positions in digital goods have been studied. [Schwartz and Chen \(2023\)](#) present three alternatives. The default firm is assumed to enjoy market power due to consumers that are inattentive or have higher switching costs. The starting point is competition bidding, where firms bid for the default position. The higher-quality firm has an incentive to bid higher than the competitors because it expects to retain more consumers. However, if higher-quality firms are the default winner they will provide

⁴⁰ European Commission, decision of 16.12.2009. – Ref. Case COMP/C-3/39.530 – Microsoft (tying), p.19

lower consumer utility than their rivals worsening consumer experience at the expense of industry monetization e.g. by increasing ad intensity. In this alternative the shape of the switching cost distribution and the heterogeneity of the product quality with alternatives determines whether the higher-quality firm wins the bidding and whether consumer surplus is higher or lower competition bidding. Beyond the possibility of considering competition bidding, their implementation goes against the DMA market fairness objective and most specifically would violate Article 6(5), which requires gatekeepers to treat their own services and those of third parties equally in ranking and indexing, applying transparent, fair, and non-discriminatory conditions. Bidding for defaults could lead to preferential treatment based on financial incentives rather than objective criteria.

An alternative to competition bidding is to assign the default position through regulation, e.g. equal shares between competitors. Compared to bidding, assigning default to a share of consumers tends to increase profits and harm consumers as competition is softened, principally because lower-quality firms now with a share of the market will substantially increase their monetization, exploiting to their default sticky consumers, which induces highest-quality firm to do the same. All consumers lose from the softened competition, and those who are assigned to the lower-quality firm suffer additional direct harm. In the scenario where product quality is not fixed but instead improves at a decreasing rate with the firm's share of users, possibly due to learning, assigning the default position to the weaker firm may then benefit consumers in the long run. However, as in the case of competitive bidding, firms will exploit consumers with high switching costs.

The third alternative presented is the choice screen case. Paradoxically, a choice screen as the one studied in this paper, is worse for the weaker firm than the default share assignation. This approach benefits consumers in the short run but may be problematic for competition and consumer welfare in the long run, if learning effects affect the quality of products. Too few consumers will choose the weaker product, ignoring the positive externality they would generate by helping the weaker firm improve its quality. The discussion under this scenario, where consumers are heterogeneous only in switching costs and where firms' qualities are distinguishable are strong assumptions. However, it applies to the case of the browser market, where users' quality misperception of Chrome and Safari does not allow smaller browsers to

capture market share and improve their quality. The latter is most relevant in the case of the search engine market but also applies to browser innovation and the creation of a developers/user ecosystem.

In order to restore competition within the browser market, policy makers should consider the fact that this digital product is more of an experienced good and consider how interventions can impact consumers' exposure to their different alternatives. The main reason for the power of the default position is not the resulting quality improvement, but the action of preventing the use of alternatives and belief quality corrections.

The limitation of the choice screen is that doesn't offer a higher exposure, other than listing the alternatives and their descriptions. A possible approach to this problem is to mandate that a non-dominant firm be set as the default -similar to the default assignment of [Schwartz and Chen \(2023\)](#) – but followed by a requirement of present a choice screen after some time of the designation, this will allow consumer to experience an alternative before making an active choice, creating a comparison point, reducing endowment effect.

This idea was replicated in [Allcott et al. \(2025\)](#) using the search engine Bing instead of Google. They found that this policy reduces Google's market share by 16,7% while leaving consumer surplus essentially unchanged. While choice screens increase consumer surplus by a modest amount, they have almost no effect on market shares. Changing defaults, on the other hand, has a large effect on market shares, but only at the expense of a large decrease in consumer surplus. A combination of both strategies seems an appropriate remedy approach.

The results of this paper have important limitations. First, the DiD model is based on total market share. While this is convenient to observe the overall dynamics, it doesn't take into consideration the implementation of Google's choice screen remedy on Android phones. Using Google compliance definitions, the proportion of Android users that saw the choice screen at the time of this investigation is small relatively to the market size. However this sample could be affecting browser usage data—likely in a negative way for Chrome and in a positive way for alternative browsers such as Firefox, Opera, and Ecosia. In the case of Safari the results are robust, we know that Safari market share is not affected by Google choice screen as Safari is not available on the Android system. One way to correct for the other browser market shares would be to incorporate Android information regarding their data

implementation of the choice screen. It was decided not to use a proxy variable, such as the sales of new Android phones within the EU, based on the insights obtained from the Android Pixel phone research, where it remains unclear under what circumstances the choice screen is displayed.

An opportunity for further research lies primarily in the identification of parameters in the browser demand model, which currently limits the overall welfare analysis of the effectiveness of the remedy. While the current model allows us to illustrate four different hypotheses that could explain the steady-state market outcomes using user level decisions, identifying demand parameters would enable researchers to empirically assess the relevance of each hypothesis into the observed market share results. Furthermore, parameter identification would make it possible to run counterfactual simulations about the effectiveness of alternative policy interventions, such as randomizing the default browser position.

A focused analysis on the trade-offs of default randomization is essential to understand the potential consequences of undesired defaults. For instance, if “stickiness” effects are driven by a high quantity of inattentive users due to procrastination, a poor default browser might encourage users to search for alternatives and switch to one they prefer. Although users often lack motivation to engage with choice screens or pop-up prompts, they may be more likely to change their settings when the default browser fails to meet their expectations. In such cases, a bad default may lead to better outcomes than a merely suboptimal one. Future research could therefore enhance the welfare analysis by incorporating data on users’ past browsing experiences, beliefs about browser quality, and proxy quality variables such as ad intensity, security indicators, and additional services offered by each browser.

There is still significant room for policy innovation in digital markets, particularly regarding alternatives to choice screens and the location of policy in the market. With respect to alternatives, the choice screen has recently been one of the preferred remedies for digital policy interventions and has been evaluated in the cases of search engines in the EU, Turkey, and Russia, where its effectiveness varies across contexts. This highlights the need for forums to discuss and develop other potential policy proposals.

In terms of policy location there has been limited focus on the browser market, aside from references to the IE case in 2009. This may be due to perceived similarities with other digital markets or the assumption that the browser market is less concentrated than the search engine market. Nevertheless, it is important to recognize that effective policy interventions at the right market entry point, such as the browser market, may lead to more proactive and less reactive regulation in further markets, potentially reducing the need for future interventions. Developing an institutional framework, such as a systematic review of entry-point players and their adjacent products or services and mandating to unlink their services would help to reduce the incentives on the generations of digital ecosystem.

7. Conclusion

This paper aims to fill the research gap regarding the consequences of the DMA on the mobile browser market, with particular focus on the initial effects of the choice screen remedy implemented by Apple on iPhone devices to comply with Article 6(3) of the DMA.

The descriptive analysis shows that the introduction of the "About Your Default Browser" screen resulted in exponential growth in downloads of all alternative browsers shown on the choice screen. However, despite the number of alternatives and randomized position, this empirical analysis shows that Chrome has not only maintained but even strengthened its leading position by increasing its market share of downloads in the mobile App Store.

In terms of browser usage, the dominant players Chrome and Safari retained their market share levels in the mobile market, with only modest short-term shifts in overall market share following the implementation of the remedy. These findings underscore that while the screen remedy had immediate quantitative effects, the long-term competitive landscape remains largely unchanged.

Behavioral factors such as consumer procrastination, inattention, and, most notably, naive beliefs about the quality of alternative browsers shape user behavior into a steady-state usage pattern. These findings suggest that mere exposure to the names of the alternative choices is insufficient unless accompanied by strategies that correct consumer beliefs, such as creating comparative frameworks or more effectively incentivizing experience with alternatives.

Regarding the differences found between Apple's and Google's compliance reports, it is important to highlight the necessity of including more detailed specifications in the requirements for the architectural design of the choice screen. Without clear guidance, elements such as the timing of the implementation limit the potential scope and impact of the remedy.

Based on the empirical results of this research and recent literature on choice screens, a revision of the effectiveness of the choice screen and the consideration of complementary or alternative interventions is recommended. In conclusion, while the DMA represents a positive step towards enhancing market contestability through the choice screen strategy in the browser market, the modest changes following the implementation of the remedy suggest the need for further refinement of this approach. Future research should expand on the welfare implications of such interventions, ensuring a careful balance between regulatory actions and the preservation of incentives for innovation.

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9. Appendix

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Appendix A. Tables

Table A.1 List of DMA Article 5 and 6 obligations and Prohibitions

Art.5	9 Prohibitions-obligations
5(2)	No combination of data from different services or require logging in and identification without user consent sought once p.a.
5(3)	No wide and narrow MFNs/parity clauses
5(4)	No anti-steering : allow business users to communicate w users off the platform, free of charge
5(5)	No anti-disintermediate : allow access and use by end users of services even if acquired elsewhere
5(6)	No prevention of raising issues of non-compliance with public authorities
5(7)	No tying of CPS to ID services, web browser engine or payment services
5(8)	No CPS Tying : no requirements to use other core platform services
5(9)	Online ad transparency for advertisers : provide for ad placed by the advertisers prices and related metrics free of charge on daily basis
5(10)	Online ad transparency for publishers : provide for ad displayed on publisher inventory prices and related metrics free of charge on daily basis
Art.6	12 Prohibitions and obligations
6(2)	No data use in dual role : do not use data about business users to compete with them
6(3)	- Enable un-installing of apps on OS, unless essential to OS/device, - Enable easy changing of default settings on OS, virtual assistance or browser and require initial prompt (at first use) for choice of default search engine, virtual assistant and browser
6(4)	Allow side loading : enable interoperability for third party apps and app store and allow prompts to users to make these defaults, with integrity/security defence
6(5)	No self-preferencing or discrimination in ranking , and related indexing and crawling, services and transparency around ranking criteria
6(6)	No restriction of switching or multi-homing across services accessed via the CPS – device neutrality
6(7)	Access and interoperability for providers of services or hardware to same features of OS or virtual assistant that are available to gatekeepers own services and hardware – free, unless impossible for integrity reasons
6(8)	Online ad transparency : provide performance tools and access to ad data to publishers, advertisers, free of charge
6(9)	Data portability effective, real time, free of charge
6(10)	Data access for business users to data associated with their services , real-time free of charge
6(11)	Data sharing for ranking, query, click and view data (subject to anonymization for personal data) at FRAND
6(12)	Access for business users to app stores, search engines and social networking services at FRAND + Requirement for alternative dispute settlement mechanism
6(13)	No disproportionate conditions or process for termination of service
Art.7	1 obligation
	Horizontal interoperability of basic functionalities for number independent interpersonal communications services

Table taken from *De Streel et al. (2023, p.)*

Table A.2 Treated countries, alternative samples and mobile subscriptions

Country	Treated	European Sample	European & OECD Sample	Mobile Celular Subscriptions
Albania		x	x	2610000
Andorra		x	x	126214
Australia			x	29100000
Austria	x	x	x	11100000
Belgium	x	x	x	12100000
Bosnia Herzegovina		x	x	3870000
Bulgaria	x	x	x	8010000
Canada			x	36500000
Chile			x	26700000
Colombia			x	87400000
Costa Rica			x	7440000
Croatia	x	x	x	4560000
Cyprus	x	x	x	1430000
Czechia	x	x	x	13600000
Denmark	x	x	x	7500000
Estonia	x	x	x	2050000
Finland	x	x	x	7140000
France	x	x	x	77400000
Georgia		x	x	5910000
Germany	x	x	x	105000000
Greece	x	x	x	11300000
Hungary	x	x	x	10200000
Iceland			x	478176
Ireland	x	x	x	5760000
Israel			x	14000000
Italy	x	x	x	78500000
Japan			x	219000000
Korea			x	83900000
Latvia	x	x	x	2260000
Lithuania	x	x	x	3920000
Luxembourg	x	x	x	960900
Malta	x	x	x	749302
Mexico			x	140000000
Moldova		x	x	4010000
Monaco		x	x	40538
Montenegro		x	x	1310000
Netherlands	x	x	x	21200000
New Zealand			x	6560000
Norway		x	x	6100000
Poland	x	x	x	52400000
Portugal	x	x	x	12800000
Romania	x	x	x	23135714
Serbia		x	x	8530000
Slovak republic	x	x	x	7630000
Slovenia	x	x	x	2730000
Spain	x	x	x	61200000
Sweden	x	x	x	14800000
Switzerland		x	x	10900000
Turkey		x	x	92200000
Ukraine		x	x	50300000
UK		x	x	84300000
USA			x	386000000
Total	27	40	52	35898478

Own creation; source of data mobile Subscriptions: World Bank (2024)

Table A.3 Share of iPhones with iOS17.4

	1 Marz 2024	5 Marz 2024	6 April 2024	19 April 2024	12 May 2024
Austria	0.81%	2.97%	18.80%	66.47%	75.16%
Belgium	0.80%	0.86%	15.20%	65.86%	73.42%
Bulgaria	0.48%	0.74%	16.87%	63.34%	71.99%
Croatia	0.43%	2.02%	18.39%	65.60%	73.82%
Cyprus	2.34%	1.44%	17.59%	62.96%	68.86%
Czechia	1.83%	3.74%	21.13%	67.37%	74.22%
Denmark	0.49%	0.78%	16.87%	64.88%	73.76%
Estonia	1.14%	2.82%	17.74%	64.52%	73.20%
Finland	0.84%	0.86%	20.22%	54.52%	65.78%
France	0.67%	0.95%	14.37%	58.79%	67.09%
Germany	0.81%	2.83%	21.72%	67.78%	73.67%
Greece	0.67%	2.21%	18.56%	63.30%	70.90%
Hungary	0.74%	1.04%	23.94%	68.39%	71.83%
Ireland	0.43%	0.41%	10.07%	53.36%	55.36%
Italy	0.65%	1.29%	18%	60.68%	67.87%
Latvia	1.60%	3.08%	22.26%	63.69%	67.79%
Lithuania	0.10%	0.22%	2.23%	7.94%	40.17%
Luxembourg	0.62%	0.92%	18.57%	63.68%	73.59%
Malta	0.65%	1.42%	15.27%	72.62%	76.76%
Netherlands	0.69%	0.89%	16.95%	67.01%	74.91%
Poland	1.21%	3.84%	22.83%	71.59%	78.10%
Portugal	1.07%	1.53%	18.48%	67.47%	72.36%
Romania	1.01%	1.40%	20.08%	64.14%	72.18%
Slovakia	0.99%	1.99%	25.95%	68.14%	75.81%
Slovenia	0.79%	1.43%	19.50%	66.42%	72.75%
Spain	0.44%	0.49%	15.16%	59.30%	67.73%
Sweden	0.57%	0.74%	13.97%	62%	69.38%
Average	0.85%	1.59%	17.80%	62.29%	70.31%

Own creation; source of data: Statista (2024), iOS version in different time dates.

Table A.4 Difference in differences browsers

	(1) Chrome	(2) Chrome	(3) Chrome	(4) Chrome	(5) Chrome
Sample	Europe	Europe Weighted	Europe + OECD	European + OECD Weighted	European + OECD Weighted
Treated x Post	1.2182 (1.32276)	0.672464 (1.37245)	-0.197374 (1.20076)	-0.693007 (1.29117)	-0.693007 (1.27855)
Treated					11.359349 * (6.73792)
post5marz					3.192036 ** (1.01131)
Daily & Country FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
R-squared Adj	0.94448	0.964546	0.948737	0.976703	0.10891
Observations	14274	14274	18666	18666	18666

Standard-errors clustered by Country and show in parentheses

	(1) Firefox	(2) Firefox	(3) Firefox	(4) Firefox	(5) Firefox
Sample	Europe	Europe Weighted	Europe + OECD	European + OECD Weighted	European + OECD Weighted
Treated x Post	0.102392 * (0.049425)	0.262386 ** (0.08689)	0.148282 * (0.066531)	0.160511 * (0.087215)	0.160511 * (0.087215)
Treated					0.308879 (0.217670)
post5marz					0.060214 (0.062566)
Daily & Country FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
R-squared Adj	.725021	0.891587	0.69008	0.841294	0.138461
Observations	14274	14274	18666	18666	18666

Standard-errors clustered by Country and show in parentheses

	(1) Ecosia	(2) Ecosia	(3) Ecosia	(4) Ecosia	(5) Ecosia
Sample	Europe	Europe Weighted	Europe + OECD	European + OECD Weighted	European + OECD Weighted
Treated x Post	-0.018328 (0.019668)	0.041925 * (0.021683)	0.012123 (0.013326)	0.063783 ** (0.019901)	0.043433 * (0.021357)
Treated					0.102836 ** (0.035432)
post5marz					0.008941 * (0.043433)
Daily & Country FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
R-squared Adj	0.662638	0.881037	0.654172	0.882038	0.310812
Observations	10796	10796	14364	14364	14364

Standard-errors clustered by Country and show in parentheses

	(1) Opera	(2) Opera	(3) Opera	(4) Opera	(5) Opera
Sample	Europe	Europe Weighted	Europe + OECD	European + OECD Weighted	European + OECD Weighted
Treated x Post	0.009405 (0.052228)	0.151183 *** (0.035031)	0.019325 (0.047707)	0.174672 *** (0.038731)	0.174672 *** (0.038353)
Treated					0.535786 * (0.316661)
post5marz					-0.046939 * (0.020200)
Daily & Country FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
R-squared Adj	0.847651	0.942008	0.847682	0.950787	0.14286
Observations	14274	14274	18666	18666	18666

Standard-errors clustered by Country and show in parentheses

	(1) Edge	(2) Edge	(3) Edge	(4) Edge	(5) Edge
Sample	Europe	Europe Weighted	Europe + OECD	European + OECD Weighted	European + OECD Weighted
Treated x Post	0.016134 (0.023632)	0.018997 (0.0155)	0.002675 (0.021604)	-0.046764 (0.035667)	-0.046764 (0.035318)
Treated					-0.082323 * (0.046370)
post5marz					0.109696 ** (0.034501)
Daily & Country FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
R-squared Adj	0.320168	0.57265	0.34564	0.63747	0.123488
Observations	14274	14274	18666	18666	18666

Standard-errors clustered by Country and show in parentheses

Robustness	(1) Samsung	(2) Samsung	(3) Samsung	(4) Samsung	(5) Samsung
Sample	Europe	Europe Weighted	Europe + OECD	European + OECD Weighted	European + OECD Weighted
Treated x Post	-0.333675 (0.228907)	-0.044511 (0.182525)	0.087425 (0.189645)	0.15754 (.103704)	0.15754 (.102691)
Treated					1.306532 (1.726650)
post5marz					-0.153304 * (0.071936)
Daily & Country FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
R-squared Adj	0.801232	0.94482	0.938249	0.991441	0.016425
Observations	14274	14274	18666	18666	18666

Standard-errors clustered by Country and show in parentheses

Appendix B. Figures

Figure B.1 Remedy Screenshots after selecting a new default browser.

iPhone screen shots, Source of data: iPhone SE, Mobile Set-up project, DICE HHU (2024)

Figure B.2 iOS Update, upgrade notification enforced.

Image taken from Apple Platform deployment.

Figure B.3 Market share DiD coefficients for treated countries.

Own creation. Source of data; Statista (2024). Blue line represents 31 periods after treatment release (enforcement day). 95% Confidence interval

Figure B.4 Event study estimators. Heterogeneity treatment effect

Own creation; source of data: Statista & AppTweak (2024). Solid line represent 31 periods after treatment release (enforcement day). 95% Confidence interval.

Figure B.5 Treatment effect by country.

Own creation; Source of data: Statista (2024). 99% Confidence Interval. DiD incorporating country and day fixed effects

Appendix C. Difference in Difference (DiD) assumptions

For the DiD model, it is assumed that: (1) SUTVA holds, meaning there are no spillover effects—the treatment of one country does not affect the designation or results of other countries (no interference). (2) No anticipation effects ([Callaway & Sant’Anna, 2021](#)) users do not change their behavior before and because of the treatment. (3) Orthogonality of treatment assignment ([Khandker et al. 2009](#)) the treatment designation is not correlated with pre-treatment characteristics such as market size, browser concentration, or past trends. (4) Parallel Trends Assumption—in the absence of treatment, the treated and control groups would have followed similar pre-treatment trends, ensuring that the estimated treatment effect is not driven by pre-existing differences. Visually it is rejected the hypothesis of different parallel trends. A second analysis and to probe our visual results, it is used a simple test for differential parallel trend from [Riveros-Gavilanes \(2023\)](#) where.

$$Y_{bct} = \lambda_c + \gamma_t + \alpha(D_{ct}^{pre} * T_{bct}) + \tau(D_{bct}^{post} * T_{bct}) + \varepsilon_{ct}$$

Where Y_{bct} is the outcome value, in our case the browser market for each browser b in country c in time t . λ_c represent the country’s fixed effect, γ_t the time fix effects. α is the coefficient of interest for the test, which captures the differences in the slopes in the pre intervention period between the treatment and control groups relative to the reference point. This point is time is selected as $t-1$ from release day. D_{bit}^{pre} is the dummy variable which identifies the pre intervention period. T_{bct} is the dummy variable which identifies if country c has ever received the treatment or not. The coefficient τ is a measure of the generic average treatment effect on the treated after the intervention.

The hypothesis is $H0: \alpha = 0$ or the absence of significant differences in the slopes of treatment and control group (Parallel trends Hypothesis) relative to the reference period. Graphic A2.1 presents the Safari coefficient plot of the trend differences between treated and control groups over time, taking as reference 4 Marz 2024 one day before treatment. In the graph it can be observed that the coefficients don’t have any type of relation and are not statistically different from 0. Other browsers

follow the same behaviour⁴¹. In table “Test of Parallel pre-trends for a DiD” is presented the results of the equation for all browsers, where the coefficient α captures the estimates of the potential differential pre trends in average. We fail to reject the null hypothesis $H_0: \alpha = 0$ for all browsers, meaning that parallel trend assumption holds.

As mentioned Tau represents the average differential trend change in the outcome after the treatment and after controlling for pre-trends. Due to no p-value Is significant the treatment does not appear to have an effect in the trend post treatment. Result that visually is confirmed with the market share plots.

Tab. Test of parallel pre-trends for a DiD

		Estimates	Std Error*	T-statistic	P-Value
Safari	Pre (α)	0.5718116	0.896322	0.637954	0.525142
	Post (τ)	1.1509218	1.329829	0.865466	0.387892
Chrome	Pre (α)	-0.1845342	0.891817	-0.206919	0.836546
	Post (τ)	-0.8164288	1.445248	-0.564906	0.572815
Opera	Pre (α)	0.0494824	0.159732	0.309783	0.757450
	Post (τ)	0.0198187	0.181046	0.109468	0.912949
Edge	Pre (α)	-0.0820850	0.073012	-1.124272	0.263921
	Post (τ)	-0.0719222	0.089774	-0.801149	0.424062
Firefox	Pre (α)	-0.0676036	0.111138	-0.608286	0.544547
	Post (τ)	0.0733268	0.099500	0.736955	0.462073

* Robust standard errors clustered at the country level

⁴¹ Plot for differences in trend between treated and control group for other browser in the resource page <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14790405>

Appendix D. Choice screen updates

Apple announced in October 2024 that it would introduce changes into the choice screen architecture through a new screen in the iOS 18.2 update⁴² set to be released on December 11, 2024.

Some of the modifications with respect to the studied screen (iOS17.4) are.

New Screen “About your default browser” for update iOS18.2

Images taken from apple developer browser choice screen.

- Browsers are displayed now with their descriptive information
- Users will be able to select their default browser directly on the choice screen, without redirecting into App store
- Users will be able to review each browser’s App Store product page by tapping on the chevron (>) to the right.

If Safari is currently in the user’s Dock or on the first page of the Home Screen and the user selects a browser that is not currently installed on their device from the choice screen, the selected browser will replace the Safari icon in the user’s Dock or in the Home Screen. If the user selects a browser that is currently installed on their device from the choice screen but not on the first page of the Home Screen or the Dock, the selected browser will replace the Safari icon in the user’s Dock or in the Home Screen.

If Safari is currently in the user’s Dock or on the first page of the Home Screen and the user had previously selected another other browser as their default from the choice screen before updating to iOS 18.2, they will be prompted once upon first launch of Safari about whether they want to swap

⁴² All details can be found on <https://developer.apple.com/support/browser-choice-screen/>

Safari's icon with the icon of their default browser. This is only if their default browser is not on the first page of the home screen or the Dock.

Developers of browsers on the choice screen will have access to a new set of data about their browser's performance on the choice screen. Developers should contact their Apple representative or dma-data@apple.com for more information.

Appendix E. Demand model.

The model from [Allcott et al. \(2025\)](#) is adapted to the browser market where consumer index i choose a browser j from a set of possible options $j \in \{d, \dots, n\}$ in two-week periods indexed by t . Each user has been assigned to a default browser $d \in \{d, \dots, n\}$, (iPhone - Safari) and the alternative browsers available for that OS is then are denoted as $\forall j' \in \{1, \dots, n\} \neq j$.

The price of agent i for using browser j is p_{ijt} . Variables a_j^* , o_{kj}^* and ξ_j^* refer to browser j ad load, number of services offered in browser j (VPN, Security protection, cashback⁴³), and other j unobserved characteristics for the research, for example UX. Browser quality then ζ_j^* is defined as $\zeta_j^* = \alpha a_j^* + \rho_k o_{kj}^* + \xi_j^*$ and agent utility i can be represented as.

$$u_{ijt}^* = \gamma p_{ijt} + \zeta_j^* + \chi_{ij}$$

The term p_{ijt} is the price that consumer i pay for using browser j , The term χ_{ij} is an individual idiosyncratic preference shifter about j browser that does not vary across time periods. Users may be imperfectly informed about browser qualities; it is use then $E_{it}[\zeta_j^*]$ to denote agent i expectation regarding browser j quality.

The majority of consumers don't pay for browser usage, then we set browser j price as $p_{ijt} = 0$ ⁴⁴. Thus the agent i utility for using free browser version j in time t will be denoted by

$$u_{ijt} = E_{it}[\zeta_j] + \chi_{ij}$$

It is assumed that iPhone users have correct beliefs about their default browser d , Safari. So $E_{it}[\zeta_d] = \zeta_d^*$ and $u_{idt} = u_{idt}^*$. Consumers face a decision regarding continuing using the default option or use an alternative one from set $\forall j' \in \{1, \dots, n\} \neq j$. To simplify the model, we assume that each user compares their default browser with their user best alternative browser j' at time t ⁴⁵. iPhone consumer i that have never used a browser other than their default Safari, may be imperfectly informed about other browsers' quality. In that case, perceived quality $E_{it}[\zeta_{j'}]$ takes a different value $\check{\zeta}_{j'} := \alpha \check{a}_{j'} +$

⁴³ Cashback could be included in price, but the rewards offered are so modest that they can be understood as marketing strategy modeled as part of the quality benefits.

⁴⁴ Browser premium options where consumers paid a monthly subscription can be modeled as well letting p_{ijt} .

⁴⁵ From the alternative set of options $\forall j' \in \{1, \dots, n\} \neq j$ browsers not aware for consumer i are set to $E_{it}[\zeta_{j'}] = -\infty$. For all other cases $u_{ijt} > 0$. Best alternative browser would be choose as the result of iterated alternative elimination. Under the case that user i is not aware of alternative browsers, it would continue with default browser d . Assumption of non-exploratory case.

$\xi_{j'}$. If consumer switch to j' , after one period consumer would correct j' quality beliefs so $E_{it}[\zeta_{j'}] = \zeta_{j'}^*$.

There are two sources of inertia. A switching cost σ of changing the default. And a fraction ϕ of users that are captive of the default firm whatever that default is. The remaining fraction $1 - \phi$ of users are probabilistically inattentive. In each period t , with exogenous probability π they are attentive and consider to change their default browser, and with probability $1 - \pi$ they are inattentive. For the consumer that is attentive in period t , they will choose the browser that maximizes their utility over an infinite horizon with per-period discount factor δ :

$$y_{it} = \arg \max_{j \in \{d, j'\}} \{u_{ijt} - \sigma 1_{j \neq y_{i,t-1}} + \delta v_{i,t+1}(j)\}$$

Where $v_{i,t+1}(j)$ is the perceived continuation value after having chosen to continue to the default browser d or changing to an alternative browser j' .

To simplify the dynamic problem into a static one, is considered that (i) Users switch (stay) permanently to the browser that give them more utility in time t (no further exploration), (ii) users weakly underestimate the quality of the alternative browser ($\tilde{\zeta}_{j'} \leq \zeta_{j'}^*$), (iii) market share are steady at $t = 0$ this assumption is relevant for the alternative consideration, factor of browser market awareness, (iv) users don't recur into multi-homing. Given these assumptions the consumer's decision is effectively static: if it's optimal to switch in the future, it's optimal to switch now. Then consumer browser decision depends on the perceived discounted utility for each browser.

$$y_{it} = \arg \max_{j \in \{d, j'\}} \left\{ \frac{u_{ijt}}{1 - \delta} - \sigma 1_{j \neq y_{i,t-1}} \right\}$$

The perceived discounted utility from permanently continuing with the default search engine and the utility from permanently switching to the alternative browser are:

$$\frac{\zeta_d^* + \chi_{id}}{1 - \delta}, \quad \frac{\tilde{\zeta}_{j'} + \chi_{ij'}}{1 - \delta} - \sigma$$

Defining the variable differences between real qualities $\Delta \tilde{\zeta}^* := \zeta_{j'}^* - \zeta_d^*$, idiosyncratic consumer preferences $\Delta \chi_i := \chi_{ij'} - \chi_{id}$, we also define the change in the perceived quality $\Delta \tilde{\zeta} := \tilde{\zeta}_{j'} - \zeta_d^*$, since users always perceive the utility of the default browser correctly ζ_d^* . An attentive consumer switches to the alternative option if

$$\Delta \tilde{\zeta} + \Delta \chi_i - \sigma(1 - \delta) > 0,$$

Therefore, the probability that a consumer that pays attention chooses an alternative browser is $P(\Delta \tilde{\zeta} - \sigma(1 - \delta) > -\Delta \chi_i)$. Defining $S(\cdot)$ as the cumulative density function of $-\Delta \chi_i$ this becomes $S(\Delta \tilde{\zeta} - \sigma(1 - \delta))$. Thus at time $t = 0$, j' market share is

$$s_{j',0} = (1 - \phi) S(\Delta \tilde{\zeta} - \sigma(1 - \delta))$$

From j' market share equation it can be illustrated four hypotheses why market share where in a steady state after remedy implementation (i) Safari has a higher real quality than the alternative browser ($\Delta\zeta^* < 0$), (ii) consumers perceive the alternative browser quality to be worse than it actually is ($\bar{\zeta}_{j'} < \zeta_{j'}^*$), (iii) Safari switching cost σ is large, or (iv) The fraction ϕ of permanently inattentive users is large. The optimal choices are the counterfactual case where users know the true quality value of all browsers $E_{it}[\zeta_{j \in \{d, \dots, n\}}] = \zeta_{j \in \{d, \dots, n\}}^*$ and make active choices with $\sigma = 0$, no switching cost.